

The National Roma Inclusion Strategy in the Republic of Croatia Monitoring Manual

EUROPEAN UNION

GOVERNMENT OF THE
REPUBLIC OF CROATIA
Office for Human Rights and
Rights of National Minorities

CENTRE FOR PEACE STUDIES

IPA 2012

Fulfilling conditions for Roma integration on the local/
regional and the national level. This publication was made
with financial support from the European Union and the
Government Office for Human Rights and the Rights of
National Minorities.

The National Roma Inclusion Strategy in the Republic of Croatia Monitoring Manual

ORIGINAL TITLE:

Priručnik za praćenje Nacionalne strategije za uključivanje Roma u Republici Hrvatskoj

NASLOV IZVORNIKA:

Priručnik za praćenje Nacionalne strategije za uključivanje Roma u Republici Hrvatskoj

PUBLISHER: Centre for Peace Studies

FOR PUBLISHER: Cvijeta Senta

EDITORS: Sandra Benčić and Niko Vrdoljak

TRANSLATION: Ziraha usluge d.o.o.

GRAPHIC DESIGN AND PREPARATION: kuna zlatica

PRESS: Kerschhoffset Zagreb Ltd.

CIRCULATION: 250

Zagreb, July 2018

IZDAVAČ: Centar za mirovne studije

ZA IZDAVAČA: Cvijeta Senta

UREDNICI: Sandra Benčić i Niko Vrdoljak

PRIJEVOD: Ziraha usluge d.o.o.

GRAFIČKO OBLIKOVANJE I PRIPREMA: kuna zlatica

TISAK: Kerschhoffset Zagreb d.o.o.

NAKLADA: 250 komada

Zagreb, srpanj 2018.

CIP record is available in the computer catalogue of the National and University Library in Zagreb under the CIP number 001003495

ISBN 978-953-7729-57-8

CIP zapis je dostupan u računalnome katalogu Nacionalne i sveučilišne knjižnice u Zagrebu pod brojem 001003495

ISBN 978-953-7729-57-8

EUROPEAN UNION

GOVERNMENT OF THE
REPUBLIC OF CROATIA
Office for Human Rights and
Rights of National Minorities

CENTRE FOR PEACE STUDIES

ECORYS

This publication was created with the financial support of the European Union, within the framework of the project "Collection and monitoring of the base line data for effective implementation of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy" implemented under the IPA 2012 Program "Fulfilling the conditions for Roma integration at the local/ regional and the national level".

The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the community of bidders, Ecorys Croatia Ltd. and the Centre for Peace Studies, and does not necessarily represent the position of the European Union and the Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities of the Government of the Republic of Croatia.

CONTENT

1/ INTRODUCTION	page 5
2/ DATA LAYOUT IN THE CROATIAN NATIONAL ROMA INCLUSION STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION MONITORING SYSTEM	page 17
NRIS Review	19
Population characteristics	19
NRIS strategic areas and general purpose indicators	20
Specific goals and indicators overview.....	21
Action plan review	22
Action plan structure.....	23
Overview of the strategic area and its elements for anonymous users.....	24
Web interface login	30
Overview of the strategic area and its elements for registered users.....	31
Annual Action Plan implementation report reviews.....	34
3/ ENTERING MEASURE CONTENT AND INDICATORS FOR THE IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES	page 43
Implementation of the Action plan measures	44
New measure implementation.....	45
Entering the indicator value	46
Entering financial items related to the measure implementation.....	48
Introduction: attachments linked to the implementation of the measure.....	52
Overview of attachments related to the implementation of the measure	52
Setting up a new attachment related to the implementation of the measure.....	53
Edit attachments.....	54
Delete attachments.....	56

4/	LOCKING THE MEASURE (FOR IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES)	page 57
	Locking the measure.....	58
5/	EXPORT MEASURE DATA (FOR IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES)	page 61
	Export measure data.....	62
6/	REVIEW OF AVAILABLE MEASURES AND UPLOADING ATTACHMENTS TO THE MEASURES FOR CO-IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES	page 65
	Review of measure implementation data	66
	Adding a new attachment to the measure by Co-Implementing authority.....	69
	Editing the attachment to the measure by Co-Implementing authority.....	72
	Editing attachments by the Administrator or Co-Implementing authority.....	73
7/	OVERVIEW OF THE EUROPEAN UNION FRAMEWORK AND LINKING THE ATTACHMENTS TO THE ASSESSMENT OF THE THEMATIC AREA	page 75
	Review of the EU Framework data	76
	Setting up a new attachment on the assessment of the thematic area	78
	Edit attachments.....	81
	Delete attachments.....	82
8/	REFERENCES	page 83

1 / INTRODUCTION

The overall goal of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy (NRIS) for the period 2013-2020¹ is to “improve the position of the Roma national minority in the Republic of Croatia by reducing the multidimensional socioeconomic gap between the Roma and the rest of the population and in a harmonized, open and transparent manner achieve full inclusion of Roma in all segments of society and the community”. NRIS is aligned with the European Union Framework for National Roma Inclusion Strategies by 2020 (EU Framework).² The Framework planned a comprehensive approach by closely linking the fight against Roma discrimination and the promotion of their social and economic inclusion.

The EU Framework has been developed to include issues of the Roma minority in the European Strategy for Europe 2020. It was developed in 2011, followed by the 2013 Recommendations of the Council of the European Union. The Framework emphasized that the social and economic integration of Roma is a two-way process which should involve as many people as possible and more actively include members of the Roma national minority. The focal point highlighted in the EU framework is to break **the vicious cycle of poverty moving from one generation to the next**. Previous strategies and measures did not make a tangible difference in the daily life of Roma, and the non-discrimination measure, on its own, was proven as insufficient for combatting exclusion.

The EU Framework, and the Recommendations for the Development of the National Policies of the EU Member States which derived from it, has set out goals related to **social and economic integration**, emphasising the following core areas: access to **education, employment, health and social protection and housing**. The Framework also envisaged horizontal policy measures such as: anti-discrimination, protection of Roma women and children, reduction of poverty through social investment, and empowering Roma and Romani women to assume a more active role in bringing about change. The structural measures of these Recommendations emphasize the importance of local actions, the work of equal treatment bodies (legal counselling, access to justice), contact points for integration, inter-state cooperation, and particularly the **development of a monitoring and evaluation methodology**.

The 2013-2020 National Roma Inclusion Strategy (NRIS) was adopted by the Government of the Republic of Croatia at the end of 2012, while the Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy for the period 2013-2015. (NRIS AP) was adopted in early 2013.³

NRIS AP, in principle, follows the structure of NRIS, where all key strategic areas were covered by corresponding chapters within the NRIS AP, with an additional chapter enti-

¹ Government of the Republic of Croatia, *National Roma Inclusion Strategy, for the period from 2013 to 2020*, Zagreb, November, 2012, <https://pravamanjina.gov.hr/UserDocImages/arhiva/National%20strategija%20za%20ukljucivanje%20Roma%20za%20razdoblje%20od%202013.%20-%202020.pdf> (27. 5. 2018)

² European Commission, *An EU Framework for National Roma Integration Strategies up to 2020*, COM (2011) 173/4, Brussels, 2011, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0173&from=EN> (21.5.2018.)

³ The Government of the Republic of Croatia, *Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy for the period 2013 to 2015*, Zagreb, 2013.

tled “Enhancing statistical data collection”, which was a specific feature of the Croatian National Strategy in relation to the strategies of other Member States, as noted in the Evaluation of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy in the Republic of Croatia.⁴

In addition, the Government of the Republic of Croatia has set up an Implementation Monitoring Committee for the 2013-2020 National Roma Inclusion Strategy, to monitor the operational part of the entire NRIS implementation, while the overall co-ordination and monitoring of policies and activities targeted at the Roma national minority, on the national level, was entrusted to the Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities of the Government of the Republic of Croatia.

At the end of 2014 and early 2015, the Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities conducted an external evaluation of the Strategic and Implementing documents. As stated by the authors, the overall objective of this evaluation was to “assess the extent to which the National Roma Inclusion Strategy for the period 2013-2020 and the Action Plan for Implementation of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy for the period 2013-2015 contributed to the inclusion of Roma national minority in the Republic of Croatia and/or to what extent could it contribute to this inclusion in the future.”⁵

Conclusions of the evaluations were that, despite of the considerable attention given to the issues of monitoring and evaluation in the National Strategy and the Action Plan, there was no comprehensive data collection system in relation to the implementation of the measures planned and the achievement of strategic goals, while the Monitoring Committee or its Working Group were not actively involved in monitoring and evaluation. Furthermore, the overview of the implemented measures presenting the results at the central, regional and local level was not available. The evaluation also, stated that there was obviously some hesitation regarding the collection of ethnically disaggregated data, and that the absence of a functional monitoring system at the general level, as well as, a concrete problem of resistance to the collection of ethnically disaggregated data, were the reason for speculating that institutions were less active in the implementation of the Action Plan than it really is the case.

During the time of the 2015 evaluation, the situation was such that the only areas of the Action Plan where the data was available for all measures were “Education” and “Program Compliance with International Standards and Accepted Agreements in Human and Minority Rights”. In several other areas, data was unavailable for most of the measures.

Therefore, one of the main recommendations of the Evaluation (Recommendation 11) **defines the base line data** to NRIS progress in measuring the achievement of the Action

4 Friedman, E., Horvat, M., *Evaluation Report: Evaluation of the National Strategy of the Republic of Croatia for Roma Inclusion*, Zagreb, Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities, UNDP Office of Croatia, 2015.

5 Friedman, E., Horvat, M., *Evaluation Report: Evaluation of the National Strategy of the Republic of Croatia for Roma Inclusion*, Zagreb, Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities, UNDP Office of Croatia, 2015.

Plan objectives (and the National Strategy as well). The evaluation report mentions 2011 census and the 2011 Regional Survey on Roma by UNDP/World Bank/European Commission as a potential source of baseline data for the current Action Plan.⁶

With this aim, the Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities, in the year 2016, launched a call for proposals under IPA 2012: **“Collection and monitoring of the base line data for effective implementation of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy”**. Within the project, a survey was conducted with the aim to define the base line data for the NRIS and NRIS Action Plan at the national, regional and local level, identify the needs of Roma communities, as well as obstacles to the inclusion of the Roma national minority at local/regional and national level. The survey encompassed **1550 Roma households, thorough interviews and focus groups** with representatives of the Roma national minority, civil society organizations and institutions from 12 counties of the Republic of Croatia. The questionnaire in the survey included the implementation monitoring indicators listed in the separate chapter «Implementation Monitoring Framework». The obtained quantitative and qualitative high-quality data should be the basis for creating the new Action Plan, but also for the drafting of the new Roma Inclusion Strategy after 2020. It should be emphasized that this extensive base line data collection effort for one of the most socially vulnerable groups and investment in this research was a pioneering effort in identifying socio-economic conditions of the Roma population in Croatia. Likewise, this method of base line data collection about groups for which the data does not exist or was not collected (due to the lack of ethnically disaggregated statistical data) is an example of good practice for improving policy tracking for marginalized groups.

PURPOSE AND GOAL OF PUBLIC POLICY MONITORING

In the context of public policies, the term “monitoring” is defined as: “an activity in a systematic and continuous collection, analysis and use of information for the purpose of controlling, identifying and taking corrective measures in the implementation of policies and regulations”.

The purpose of monitoring is to correct deviations from the set tasks, thus improving the implementation of a relative public policy and facilitate further development of the process. Monitoring is carried out at all levels of administration, with emphasis on: used resources/investments used (input monitoring); planned activities and/or implementation processes (performance monitoring) and results monitoring. Monitoring is an intensive and dynamic process of managing programs and projects, resulting in systematic periodic reporting of findings, estimates, conclusions and recommendations on the achieved progress and the benefits expected from the implementation of programs and projects. Public policy monitoring supports the process of managerial decision-making on the

⁶ Friedman, E., Horvat, M., Evaluation Report: Evaluation of the National Strategy of the Republic of Croatia for Roma Inclusion, Zagreb, Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities, UNDP Office of Croatia, 2015.

basis of continuous information flow. The main task of monitoring public policies is to monitor and measure the achievement of their goals and effectiveness in the process of their implementation. It is possible to adjust the way public policy is implemented in a timely manner on the account of implementation monitoring results. Continuous monitoring which takes place in several phases has an important role in long-term public policies and programs. The realization of each successive phase may be preceded with the monitoring and evaluation of activities and results of the preceding stages. In the context of survey questions, the term “assessment” is defined as: “assessment of public policies and programs based on their results, impact and needs, which they intend to fulfil”.

Monitoring and evaluating public policies are instruments of good governance in the implementation of governance at all levels. Prerequisites for their effectiveness is to consider them as an integral part of the decision-making process and management of the overall development, implementation, and public policies evaluation cycle.⁷

Traditionally, the implementation phase is the phase following the formulation and adoption of a public policy proposal, and the monitoring meant to track success or failure in relation to the set goals. Today, the implementation is not merely the stage following the formulation and adoption of a public policy proposal, but the awareness of interrelationship between these two phases is being raised; a phased public policy model is being upgraded with “more open conceptualization that reduces the risk of implementation being narrowed down to dichotomous contrast of success versus failure to achieve the set goals, but is at the same time considered as a process, that is, a series of decisions and activities in the implementation of that decision.”⁸ Hill and Hupe suggest a *multiple governance framework* as an analytical framework for use in public policy implementation.⁹ This framework is seen as an operational management of the process of achieving collectively set goals and public policy objectives, which includes activities on system, organizational and individual level. In doing so, the creation of instruments and frameworks for functioning of formal and informal actors involved in policy implementation is part of *policy-making* process management at the system level.¹⁰

Based on the above, it follows that the actors in the process of monitoring certain public policies must provide feedback between the implementation phase and the formulation phase – in this way public policies become a “living instrument” and the implementation encompasses the totality of the process, which on the basis of the monitoring findings, affects the (re) formulation of the set outcomes of the specific public policy. This achieves the agility effect necessary to ensure real effects and outcomes of policies in relation to the needs of the target group/s in constantly and rapidly changing environment. This is particularly important within the framework of long-term policies such as NRIS.

⁷ Kresnaliyska, G., Monitoring of Public Policies - A Modern Tool of Good Governance, *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, god.5, br. 5, 2015, str 43-47.

⁸ Kekez Koštro, A., Što se misli pod implementacijom javnih politika?, *Političke analize*, 2015, br.13, p. 65-67.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

The eight-year implementation framework requires the adjustment of the set results, changes of the monitoring indicators when possible, and the adaptation of measures to emerging circumstances, needs and problems of target groups.

If all the above is applied to the implementation of NRIS, we see that the purpose of the monitoring is to provide feedback on the feasibility and the effects of the set goals and expected outcomes and their reformulation to match the actual changes in target communities. This particularly applies to the Action Plan as the key implementation instrument of NRIS and the corresponding documents at the regional and local level. For this reason, the survey conducted to collect the base line data should be seen as one of the means for providing participatory monitoring to all stakeholders, to be used as a tool that provides insight into the initial state of affairs and detect priority investments at local, regional and national level to ensure the reduction of the socio-economic gap between the Roma and the general population.

BASIC TOOLS FOR PUBLIC POLICY MONITORING

Policy monitoring, as stated by Daniela Širinić in the Public Policy Monitoring Handbook,

“implies an assessment of the efficiency and successfulness of the implementation by comparing the actual status with the logical implementation model (logic of intervention). Based on the performance criteria, monitoring will determine the ratio between the funds invested and the policy results achieved, regardless of the long-term policy goals content, while the degree of achievement of the desired effects is determined by the performance monitoring criteria, regardless of the funds and instruments used to achieve the goals or the results. While the performance is partially impacted by the value contribution of policy, in terms of contributing results to the achievement of effects, the efficiency measures only the productivity of the policy implementation. Of course, these criteria are complementary as they cover different policy implementation dimensions, while the efficiency refers to monitoring the cost-effectiveness of the implementation process, the performance is related to monitoring the implementation effects. In this sense, a policy may be efficient and unsuccessful, but also successful and inefficient. Two distinct types of monitoring arise from this difference; the implementation-based monitoring, or process monitoring focused on input analysis, implementation of instruments and outputs, as well as monitoring of effects aimed at analysis of the public policy effects on the operational objectives of each instrument.”

The basic prerequisite and recommendation for successful monitoring is the development of a **Monitoring Plan** with clear, measurable, accessible, relevant implementation performance indicators that encompass two types of indicators: base-line value and target value. Even though the NRIS contained the special chapter on the Strategy

¹¹ Širinić, D., *Priručnik za praćenje javnih politika za organizacije civilnog društva*, Centar za mir, nenasilje i ljudska prava – Osijek, Osijek, 2016., p. 27.

implementation monitoring, it did not contain the base line data for these types of indicators; precisely for this reason it was necessary to carry out this research in order to define the initial state, at least until the end of the implementation cycle and before programming the next cycle.

Target values, quantitatively or qualitatively, should be redefined in the new Action Plan and aligned with the base line data.

Besides the indicators, the monitoring plan should include the analysis of the stakeholders, their capacities and resources required to monitor the NRIS outcomes, the need for additional capacity building for data collection and processing, and horizontal and vertical information exchange models, information management models and joint responsibility for the quality of the collected and analysed data. Stakeholder analysis should also result in determining the type of information and data that individual stakeholders collect/process in relation to their capacities, knowledge and resources. Finally, it is necessary to define monitoring reporting levels, responsible bodies, to define different reporting formats in relation to audience to which they are intended and to reinforce elements of public presentation of findings at local, regional and national level. It is important to consider that there are large differences in monitoring capacities and implementation reporting at the level of local self-governance units, thus the capacity shortages in small administrative units need to be compensated from the regional and national levels.

THE EUROPEAN FRAMEWORK FOR ROMA INCLUSION MONITORING

In addition to strengthening the European and national frameworks for Roma integration in Europe and the common sectoral (education, employment, health, housing) and horizontal (anti-discrimination, women, youth) themes, attention has also been given to systematic monitoring of implementation of appropriate measures and activities.¹² With the activities of the Council of Europe and¹³ OESS¹⁴ including international initiati-

-
- ¹² Of course, along with reporting at the European level, the Republic of Croatia also submits a number of reports to the United Nations bodies, which often require detailed information on members of the most vulnerable groups, including members of the Roma national minority. Various committees have been set up to monitor the application of international treaties which report their activities to the General Assembly. Examples of such committees include the Committee on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination (CERD), the Committee on Human Rights, the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), the Committee Against Torture and the Committee on the Rights of the Child.
- ¹³ In addition to specific activities of the Ad hoc Committee of Experts on Roma and Traveller Issues (CAHROM), the following topics, bodies and instruments are particularly important for Roma integration: human rights protection, in particular in view of the European Convention on Human Rights, the European Committee for Prevention of Torture, the European Committee against Racism and Intolerance (ECRI), Convention on Action against Trafficking, Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse, Convention on the Prevention and Fight against Violence against Women and Home Violence, Social Rights in accordance with the European Social Charter, Language Rights in accordance with the European Charter and Regional or Minority Languages, Minority Rights in accordance with the Framework Convention for the Protection of National Minorities. More information is available on the Council of Europe web site: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/portal/roma> (5.7.2018)
- ¹⁴ More information is available at the OSCE website: <https://www.osce.org/roma-and-sinti> (5.7.2018)

ves, such as the Roma Inclusion Decade 2005-2015, the EU took a more prominent part in those processes. Therefore, in its last annual Communication of the **EUROPEAN COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL, Midterm review of the EU framework for national Roma integration strategies**¹⁵ it is stated:

“In 2011 the situation of Roma¹⁶, Europe’s largest minority (about 10-12 million people), came to the centre of political attention. In the context of the economic crisis, it became clear that tackling economic and social marginalisation and discrimination against Roma is not only a moral duty in line with fundamental EU values, but also, an economic imperative promising longterm benefits for ageing European societies. It was clear that action is needed at both national and EU levels. While Member States are primarily responsible and equipped to change the situation of their Roma communities, the Commission (in line with a call from the European Parliament)¹⁷ proposed a new targeted European level policy instrument: the EU framework for national Roma integration strategies.¹⁸”

The framework aims to close the gap between Roma and non-Roma in four key areas: education, employment, healthcare and housing. The Commission’s proposal was followed up by Council and European Council conclusions¹⁹, marking an unprecedented EU-level commitment to a comprehensive approach to Roma inclusion. Key requirements included:

- / a commitment by all Member States to developing national strategies
- / a combination of social inclusion and rights-based approaches, with the fight against discrimination becoming a horizontal requirement across all policy fields
- / the involvement of regional and local authorities, civil society and Roma in the design, implementation and monitoring of NRIS
- / adequate and sustainable funding (national budget to be supplemented by EU funds)
- / monitoring of results, and
- / mainstreaming Roma inclusion goals in public policies

In 2013, the EU Roma framework was strengthened by a Council Recommendation on effective Roma integration measures.²⁰ The Recommendation sharpened the focus on

15 European Commission, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND COUNCIL, Revision of the EU Framework for National Roma Integration Strategy in the Middle of the Programming Period, 2017, [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/HR/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0458](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/HR/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0458&from=HR) & from = HR, (July 5, 2018)

16 According to the terminology of European institutions and international organizations, the term “Roma” here signifies a number of different groups (e.g. Roma, Sinti, Kale, Gypsies, Romaniels, Boyashs, Ashkali, Egyptians, Yenias, Domi, Lomi, Abdali) including Travellers and does not deny the specificities of these groups.

17 2010/2276(INI)

18 COM(2011) 173

19 EUCO 23/11, EPSCO 10665/11. In accordance with the Council’s conclusions, all Member States are invited to “prepare, update or develop their national Roma inclusion strategy or integrated sets of policy measures within their wider social inclusion policies.” Until 2012, all member states, except Malta, have submitted strategies or integrated sets of policy measures. The terms “national Roma integration strategy” and “strategy” also include integrated sets of policy measures.

20 SL C 378

antidiscrimination and extended work on Roma to new horizontal and structural areas. It also introduced, as of 2016, an annual reporting obligation on Member States, contributing to the development of a European system of monitoring. The December 2016 Council conclusions on accelerating the process of Roma integration confirmed the Member States' commitment and called for a midterm review of the EU framework.²¹

The development of the European monitoring system has been particularly influenced by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA),²² launching in 2012 a joint questionnaire for reporting progress on Roma integration in the EU member states. The Republic of Croatia participated in these activities from 2012, and from 2014 submits regularly reports to EU/EC.

The EU has demonstrated the important role that Roma integration has in its agenda and in the preparation of the multi-annual framework for the period 2014–2020 by introducing new tools to improve the efficiency of use of the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) in terms of social inclusion, including, inter alia, Roma:

*“a new set of requirements to ensure that Member States that allocate EU funds for Roma inclusion, have national strategic Roma inclusion policy frameworks and meet the pre-conditions for their effective implementation, a more robust partnership principle (as part of a European code of conduct) to guide cooperation with civil society, local authorities and social partners in the planning, implementation and monitoring of EU-funded interventions, increased earmarked funding for capacity building for civil society organisations, obligatory minimum allocation ratios for investment in social inclusion, support for the physical, economic and social regeneration of deprived communities that may involve stronger integrated housing measures, territorial and integrated approaches addressing the specific needs of geographical areas most affected by poverty and target groups at highest risk of social exclusion, facilitated by a multi-fund approach, **enhanced results-oriented monitoring arrangements (common indicators focusing on outputs and results) and reporting on a Roma-specific investment priority, and for Member States on the use of EU funds to tackle segregation.**”²³*

The need for increased focus on the establishment of a result-based monitoring system was confirmed, inter alia, by the unsatisfactory findings of the European Court of Auditors regarding the implementation of the Roma Integration Policy from the aspect of EU funding in the financial perspective 2007–2013. Thus, the European Court of Auditors stated in its thematic report “EU policy initiatives and financial support for Roma inte-

21 European Commission, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND COUNCIL, Midterm review of the EU framework for national Roma integration strategies, p. 2-3, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/HR/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0458&from=HR>, (5.7.2018.)

22 More information is available on the Agency for Fundamental Rights website: <http://fra.europa.eu/en/theme/roma> (5.7.2018)

23 European Commission, COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND COUNCIL, Midterm review of the EU framework for national Roma integration strategies, p. 2-3, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/HR/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0458&from=HR>, (5.7.2018.)

gration: significant progress made over the last decade, but additional efforts needed on the ground”, stated: “monitoring systems provided an inadequate basis for reporting on Roma integration during the 2007-2013 programme period”^{24 25}

The recommendations of the European Court of Auditors on monitoring point out that during the next programming period or during the update of the operational programs the Commission should ensure, whenever possible, that the Roma integration goals, included in the national strategies for Roma integration, **are reflected in the ESIF framework at all operating levels**. In this context, it should ensure reliable data collection to allow monitoring and progress evaluation on the level of individual projects and all administration levels. Likewise, Member States should, if necessary, to complement the common indicators of achievement and results found in legal acts on ESIF with indicators specifically related to Roma. These **indicators should be aligned with the indicators established in the National Roma Integration Strategies and should then be used for monitoring of the 2014 – 2020 Operational Programs**. Indicators may be based on the 2016 indicators established by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. The Commission should encourage Member States to **collect statistical data on ethnic affiliation in a comprehensive manner over the next two years**, in accordance with the national legal framework and EU legislation, including possible existing deviations. Eurostat could cover relevant issues by their surveys, such as the labour force survey and within the framework of EU statistics on income and living conditions.

Based on the values and postulates resulting from these recommendations of the Court of Auditors, the Office of Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities of the Government of the Republic of Croatia took steps to establish an effective system for monitoring the effects and results achieved by the implementation of the strategy measures. The project **Collection and monitoring of the base line data for effective implementation of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy** within which this manual was drafted, creates the foundations for the entire process by collecting socio-economic data on Roma households and members of the Roma national minority, which will be integrated into the NRIS implementation monitoring system with the aim of improving the effectiveness and efficiency of Roma inclusion measures in this financial perspective already. The methodological basis for this data collection was significantly supported by the activities of the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights.

²⁴ European Court of Auditors “*EU policy initiatives and financial support for Roma integration: significant progress made over the last decade, but additional efforts needed on the ground*” nr.14, 2016: https://www.ecca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR16_14/SR_ROMA_HR.pdf (5,7.2018)

²⁵ In the context of the EU, often highlighted is the problem, partly relevant in the Republic of Croatia, that data collection on ethnicity is very limited due to legal consequences. Some European countries (e.g. Germany, France) prohibit the collection of socioeconomic data based on ethnic origin for various legal, historical and political reasons. However, the Directive 95/46/EC on personal data processing and about the free flow of such data and the Regulation (EC) no. 45/2001 on protecting individuals in connection with personal data processing in institutions and Community bodies and the free movement of such data envisages a series of exemptions from prohibiting the processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, in particular “if the subject of the data has given its explicit consent for processing of such data”. Those provisions are included in General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Under the scope of this project a web interface was developed to serve as a monitoring tool, consisting of an overview of the Action Plans containing links to the strategic NRIS areas and the possibility for input of the implementation measures, indicators and their values. Such a tool should facilitate the monitoring processes at all levels, in particular the synchronization and compilation of data at the national level. In order for the tool to contribute to the harmonization of NRIS implementation and the Action Plan, it is necessary to harmonize all local Action Plans with the national one, at least with regard to the indicator types for which the base line data now exist. The alignment of the NRIS indicators in the National and Local Action Plans would contribute to a more focused implementation, the ability to compare practices and facilitate monitoring of the measure implementation, resources and their effects.

The monitoring web interface cannot be the only dimension for monitoring implementation: it is necessary to allocate resources for the coordination of key stakeholders, to continuously strengthen their capacity for data collection/processing, to monitor and collect data from other secondary sources, and to ensure that monitoring is continuously routed into programming processes of the EU Funds (in particular the ESF and the ERDF) to integrate the identified needs of the community into the plans for financing programs/projects and local/regional and national budgets.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UPGRADING THE MONITORING SYSTEM BASED ON THE COLLECTED BASE LINE DATA

- 1/ Create a **Monitoring Plan** with clear, measurable, accessible, relevant implementation performance indicators that encompass two types of indicators: base line and target values, and sources of information for each of the above-mentioned indicators diversified and specified according to collection level (local, regional, national). The source of information list for each indicator should correspond to the collection level: indicating sources of information for respective indicators which are collected at the level of local self-government units, and sources collected at the level of state bodies, etc.
- 2/ Allocate resources for key stakeholder coordination, continuously strengthen their data collection/processing capacities, and to define secondary sources of information and ways of collecting them.
- 3/ Harmonize the NRIS and Action Plan indicators and their initial and target values to ensure that the Action Plan reporting provides aggregated data for NRIS implementation goals directly.
- 4/ The target values of the NRIS monitoring indicators, and in particular the new Action Plan, should be directly integrated in the implementation of the ESF, ERDF and EAFRD in a way that the Action Plan measures are included in the horizontal project descriptions policies (modelled upon other target groups such as people with disabilities), and to prepare projects (especially in the field of infrastructure, education and social services) specific to the Roma population, bearing in mind the

limitations on the use of funds in terms of investments in ethnically segregated communities.

- 5/ Reporting on the implementation of ESF, ERDF and EAFRD from the user level to the level of the co-ordination body should include applicable indicators from NRIS and the Action Plan in order to obtain complete data on NRIS/Action Plan objectives and measures investments.
- 6/ When it comes to regional/local investments, tenders for these three mentioned Funds should include the NRIS/Action Plan indicators into the project application evaluation forms, when applicable (when it comes to 12 counties covered by the survey), i.e. they should grant additional points to the competitors which allocate part of their investment into improving the quality of life of the Roma population.

2 / DATA LAYOUT IN THE CROATIAN NATIONAL ROMA INCLUSION STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION MONITORING SYSTEM

An overview of the basic functionalities and data on the Action plans and their implementation being kept in the system (i.e. in the web interface) for monitoring of the National Roma Inclusion Strategy implementation are available for anonymous users and for Implementing authorities/Co-implementing Authorities.

THE STEPS TO BE TAKEN ARE THE FOLLOWING

- 1/ Open the web interface for monitoring the National Roma Inclusion Strategy implementation: in your web browser (e.g. Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Internet Explorer, etc.), type the following web address: <http://nsur.hr/> and press “Enter” on the keyboard
- 2/ Once the address is entered, the homepage of the website is displayed in your web browser:

- 3/ Currently, no one is logged in the web interface, but some functionalities are also available for **anonymous users** – see the toolbar presented below:

- 4/ Place the cursor over the “**NSUR**” (**NRIS**) button to see available functions:

- / By selecting “**Pregled NSUR-a**” (**NRIS Review**), an overview of the overall structure of the current National Strategy is launched, including an overview of population characteristics, strategic areas, indicators of the overall strategic goal, specific strategic area goals and their key indicators.

- 5/ If an anonymous user (i.e. a user who **is not logged** in the system) in step 4 selects the “**Pregled nsur-a**” (NRIS Review) function, then the following screen is displayed:

The screenshot displays the 'Pregled nsur-a' (Review NSUR) page. At the top, there is a header with the NSUR logo and navigation links: 'NSUR', 'AKCIJSKI PLAN', and 'INFORMACIJE'. The main heading is 'Nacionalna strategija za uključivanje Roma za razdoblje od 2013. do 2020. godine'. Below this, there is a paragraph of text explaining the strategy's goals. To the right, there is a box titled 'Obilježja populacije' (Population Characteristics) with 'Broj pokazatelja: 2' and a 'Pregled' button. Below the text, there are three strategic areas, each in a grey box with a 'Pregled' button and a 'Broj pokazatelja' indicator:

- Strateško područje 1. Obrazovanje:** Broj pokazatelja: 2
- Strateško područje 2. Zapošljavanje i uključivanje u gospodarski život:** Broj pokazatelja: 0
- Strateško područje 3. Zdravstvena zaštita:** Broj pokazatelja: 0

- / In the image above, we can see the general goal of NRIS, the list of strategic areas and their objectives, information on the number of population characteristics indicators and the number of indicators contained in the strategic area. A summary of strategic areas is shown in “boxes” with grey background where one “box” represents one strategic area. The boxes contain basic information about strategic areas, including their **identification number, name, description and number of indicators included**.

POPULATION CHARACTERISTICS

- 6/ By selecting “View” (review) function in the “Obilježja populacije” (**Population Characteristics**) box, you will see a page containing all population characteristics indicators:

The screenshot displays the 'Pokazatelji obilježja populacije' (Population Characteristics Indicators) page. The page title is 'Pokazatelji obilježja populacije'. Below the title, there is a table with the following data:

Pokazatelj	Tip	Dodatne dimenzije	Početna vrijednost	Ciljana vrijednost
1. Prvi pokazatelj obilježja populacije	Broj	Nema	Da	Ne
2. Drugi pokazatelj obilježja populacije	Logički operator	Nema	Ne	Da

- 7/ For NRIS overview (step 5), select the “View” function within the strategic area:

- 8/ After clicking the “Pregled” (View) button within the strategic area tab (see previous step), the following screen is displayed:

- / The above image shows information about the strategic area, i.e. the general goal of the strategic area. Likewise, we can see the general goal indicators by selecting the “Pokazatelji općeg cilja” (General Goal Indicators) tab and the specific strategic area goals by selecting the “Specific Goals” tab.

- 9/ Selecting the “Pokazatelji općeg cilja” (General Goal Indicators) tab opens the following display:

Pokazatelj	Tip	Dodatna oznaka	Podatna vrijednost	Ciljna vrijednost
1.1. Prvi pokazatelj općeg cilja	Broj	Doz	Da	Ne
1.2. Drugi pokazatelj općeg cilja	Dotaz	Nema	Da	Da

10/ Selecting the “Posebni ciljevi” (Specific objectives) tab opens the following display:

/ On the “Posebni ciljevi” (Specific objectives) tab, grey boxes with information on the objective, i.e. a description of the **specific goal**, and the **number of indicators** included in the goal are visible.

11/ By selecting (mouse click) “Pregled” (**View**) function within the grey box with target information, the following screen is opened:

/ The image above shows the information about the objective and the “**Pokazatelji posebnog cilja**” (Specific objective indicators) tab.

12/ Select the “Pokazatelji posebnog cilja” (Specific objective indicators) tab to see all of the indicators included in the objective:

- 13/ Place the cursor over the “**Akcijski plan**” (**Action Plan**) button to see available functions:

- / By selecting “**Pregled akcijskog plana**” (**Action plan Overview**), an overview of the overall structure of the current Action plan is launched, including an overview of strategic areas, goals, measures and indicators
- / By selecting the “**Pregled provedbe po godinama**” (**Implementation overview by years**) function, you can see the overview of the implementation of the Action plans with the status “**Odobren**” (Approved) (if such data exist in the web interface)

ACTION PLAN REVIEW

- 14/ If an anonymous user (i.e. a user who **is not logged** in the system) in step 4 selects the “**Pregled akcijskog plana**” (**Action Plan Overview**) function, then the following screen is displayed:

- / The image above shows that the “**Akcijski plan**” (**Action plan**) tab with the summary of the Action plan contents (i.e. number of strategic areas, goals, measures and indicators included in the Action plan).

The Action plan consists of strategic areas, goals, measures and indicators that are hierarchically represented by the following diagram:

The Web Interface for monitoring the National Roma Inclusion Strategy implementation respects the above-mentioned relationships where, for example, “Strategic Areas” contain “Objectives”, where “Objectives” contain “Measures” and where “Measures” contain “Measure Performance Indicators”.

NOTE Understanding the structure of the Action plan is very important for understanding the operating concept and purpose of the web interface for monitoring the National Roma Inclusion Strategy implementation.

- 15/ If you click on the “**Strateška područja**” (**Strategic Areas**) tab in the web interface, you can see a summary of the strategic areas defined by the Action plan – see the image below:

- / A summary of strategic areas is shown in “boxes” with grey background where one “box” represents one strategic area. The boxes contains basic information about strategic areas, including their “**identifikacijski broj**” (**identification number**), “**naziv**” (**title**), “**opis**” (**description**), “**broj uključenih ciljeva**” (**number of indicators included**) and “**broj definiranih mjera**” (**number of defined measures**).

OVERVIEW OF THE STRATEGIC AREA AND ITS ELEMENTS FOR ANONYMOUS USERS

- 16/ If there is a need, it is possible to view the strategic area, i.e. to display additional details of the strategic area as follows:
- / In the box that represents a specific strategic area, you need to click the “Pregled” (View) button in the lower right corner of the tab (see the image on the left)

- 17/ After clicking the “Pregled” (View) button within the strategic area tab (see previous step), the following screen is displayed:

- 18/ If the “Ciljevi” (Goals) tab is selected on the previous screen, then the goals defined for the selected strategic area will be displayed – see the image below:

- / The image above shows the selected strategic area goals in “boxes” where one box with grey background shows one goal.
- / The boxes contain basic information about goals, including their **identification number**, **name** and **number of measures included**.
- / By clicking “Pregled” (View) button (see image on the left), in the box showing a specific objective, it is possible to activate view detail feature for that goal, i.e. to display information about that objective and showing measures included in that goal.

- / After clicking the “Pregled” (View) button in the selected box (see previous image), the following screen is displayed:

The screenshot shows a web interface for the National Roma Inclusion Strategy. At the top, there is a logo for the 'Udruga Roma u Hrvatskoj' and the text 'AKCIJSKI PLAN INFORMACIJE'. Below the header, the breadcrumb trail reads 'Početna / Akcijski plan / Statističko područje / Cilj'. The main heading is 'Cilj 1.1. Podići kvalitetu i učinkovitost obrazovanja djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine te osigurati stjecanje potrebnih znanja i vještina koje će omogućiti osobni razvoj učenika, kao i završavanje osnovnog obrazovanja s ciljem nastavka školovanja te smanjenja razlike između obrazovnih postignuća djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine u odnosu na prosječnu razinu obrazovnih postignuća svih učenika u osnovnoškolskom obrazovanju u Republici Hrvatskoj.' Below the heading, there are two tabs: 'Informacije o cilju' (selected) and 'Mjere'. Under the selected tab, there is a table with the following data:

Statističko područje	1. Obrazovanje
Oznaka	1.1
Opis cilja	Podići kvalitetu i učinkovitost obrazovanja djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine te osigurati stjecanje potrebnih znanja i vještina koje će omogućiti osobni razvoj učenika, kao i završavanje osnovnog obrazovanja s ciljem nastavka školovanja te smanjenja razlike između obrazovnih postignuća djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine u odnosu na prosječnu razinu obrazovnih postignuća svih učenika u osnovnoškolskom obrazovanju u Republici Hrvatskoj.

- / The image above shows that “Informacije o cilju” (Objective information) tab is currently selected. If the “Mjere” (Measures) tab is selected (i.e. clicked by the mouse) on the same screen, the following screen will be displayed (see image below):

The screenshot shows the same web interface as above, but with the 'Mjere' tab selected. The main heading remains the same. Below the heading, there are two tabs: 'Informacije o cilju' and 'Mjere' (selected). Under the selected tab, there are two grey boxes representing measures:

<p>Mjera 1.1.1. Stručno usavršavanje učitelja, stručnih suradnika i suradnika pomoćnika u osnovnim školama</p> <p>Nositelj mjere: Agencija za odgoj i obrazovanje</p> <p>Broj pokazatelja: 1</p> <p>Pregled</p>	<p>Mjera 1.1.2. Sufinanciranje roditeljskog udjela za pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine u integriranim programima predškolskog odgoja</p> <p>Nositelj mjere: Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja</p> <p>Broj pokazatelja: 1</p> <p>Pregled</p>
---	---

- / The screen above shows the measures (shown in grey boxes) included in the selected goal.

- 19/ If the “Mjere” (Measures) tab is selected on the screen with strategic area details (initially called up in step 7 and displayed in step 8), then the measures defined for the selected strategic area will be displayed – see the image below:

- / The image above shows the measures from the selected strategic area objective are in grey boxes where one box shows one measure.

NOTE take into account that the display of the measure in step 10 is practically identical to the one shown in step 9, although the path to these screens is different. The fact is that the system for monitoring the National Roma Inclusion Strategy implementation has different ways of reaching same object, e.g. to the same “Objective”, “Measure”, and the selected “**central object**” will always be displayed on screen (see image above), (for example, it is “Goal” in step 9 and “Strategic Area” in step 10) and an object that has a “link” to the selected object in the hierarchical structure.

20/ After selecting “Pregled”(View) in the previous step for the selected measure, the screen with measure details (see below) will be displayed:

1.1.1 Stručno usavršavanje učitelja, stručnih suradnika i suradnika pomagača u osnovnim školama

Informacije o mjeri Pokazatelji 1

Strateško područje 1. Obrazovanje

Cilj strateškog područja 1.1. Poveći kvalitetu i učinkovitost obrazovanja i brige pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine te osigurati stjecanje potrebnih znanja i vještina koje će omogućiti osobni razvoj učenika, kao i završavanje osnovnog obrazovanja s ciljem nastavka školovanja te smanjenja razlike između obrazovnih postignuća djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine u odnosu na prosječnu razinu obrazovnih postignuća svih učenika u osnovnoškolskom obrazovanju u Republici Hrvatskoj.

Nositelji Agencija za odgoj i obrazovanje

Provedbe 2019

Surovitelji • Nema suraditelja

Rok Kontinuirano

Iznos predviđenih sredstava 4.500 00 kn

Opis sredstava Opis nije unesen

Ujedinik: Foromske komisije

Preporuka EK 1.3. Take effective measures to ensure equal treatment and full access for Roma boys and girls to quality and mainstream education and to ensure that all Roma pupils complete at least compulsory education (by eliminating any school segregation).

Mjera EK

Vrsta provedbenog tijela Javno tijelo

Razina temeljnih poslova provedbenog tijela Lokalno

/ The previous image shows that “Informacije o mjeri” (Measure information) tab is currently selected. If the “Pokazatelji” (Indicators) tab is selected (i.e. clicked by the mouse) on the same screen, the following screen will be displayed (see below):

1.1.1 Stručno usavršavanje učitelja, stručnih suradnika i suradnika pomagača u osnovnim školama

Informacije o mjeri Pokazatelji 1

Pokazatelj	Tip	Dodatne dimenzije	Početna vrijednost	Ciljana vrijednost
Broj održanih stručnih usavršavanja za broj učitelja, stručnih suradnika i suradnika pomagača koji su sudjelovali na stručnim usavršavanjima	Broj	Nema	Da	Da

- / The “Indicators” tab shows the number of indicators defined for the selected measure.
- / The definition of all indicators is shown in the table below in the lower part of the screen, where attributes can be seen for each indicator:
 - / Indicator type (e.g. “Number”, “Percentage”, “Ratio”, etc.)
 - / Additional dimensions that can be defined for the indicator
 - / Is the initial value of the indicator defined (this value is used when calculating statistical indicators)
 - / Is the target value of the indicator defined (this value is used when calculating statistical indicators)

NOTE when reviewing the Action plan, the values related to the implementation of the Action plan will NOT be shown (e.g. implementation status of the measure, indicator values, financial resources spent, explanation with the measure implementation, etc., but only the STRUCTURE OF THE ACTION PLAN). For details on the implementation of the Action plan, it is necessary to select the “**Pregled provedbe po godinama**” (**Implementation overview by years**)

- 21/ In the menu, select “**Akcijski plan**” – > “**Pregled akcijskog plana**” (**Action plan – > Action plan Overview**), then click the “**Ciljevi**” (**Goals**) tab (see image below).

- / The screen shown in the image above shows goals that hierarchically belong to the selected Action plan.
- / Similar to step 10, goals are shown in grey boxes that show basic information about each goal, and by clicking on the “**Pregled**” (**View**) button, you can retrieve additional information about the selected goal.

- 22/ In the menu, select “**Akcijski plan**” – > “**Pregled akcijskog plana**” (**Action plan – > Action plan Overview**), then click the “**Mjere**” (**Measures**) tab (see image below).

- / The screen shown in the image above shows measures that hierarchically belong to the selected Action plan.
 - / Similar to step 11, measures are shown in grey boxes that show basic information about each goal, and by clicking on the “**Pregled**” (**View**) button, you can retrieve additional information about the selected goal.
- 23/ In the menu, select “Akcijski plan” –> “Pregled akcijskog plana” (Action plan –> Action plan Overview), then click the “**Ostali akcijski planovi**” (**Other Action plans**) tab (see image below).

- / If the information system contains data on multiple Action plans, you can select an Action plan to be viewed from here.

WEB INTERFACE LOGIN

- 24/ By logging into the system, the user will be assigned to a certain role (e.g. “Implementing authority”, “Co-Implementing authority” or “Administrator”), and will be able to perform additional functionalities in the system.
- / Login to the web interface starts by selecting (i.e. clicking the mouse) on the “**Prijava**” (**Login**) button in the upper right corner of the screen.
 - / After you click the “**Prijava**” (**Login**) button, you will see a box for entering your account and password (see image below).

- / After you enter the username and password, you need to click the “**Prijava**” (Login) button.
- / After a successful login as a user that has, for example, the role of “Nositelj” (Implementing authority), the title bar of the screen will look like as below:

- / The name of the logged-in user (in the example above, the “HZZ” user who has the “Nositelj” -Implementing authority role) is displayed in the right part of the bar.

OVERVIEW OF THE STRATEGIC AREA AND ITS ELEMENTS FOR REGISTERED USERS

After the user logs in to the system (see step 24), they will be able to use some of the additional functionalities briefly described below.

- 25/ The logged in user selects in the menu “**Akcijski plan**” –> “**Pregled akcijskog plana**” (Action Plan –> Action Plan Overview), then click the “**Mjere**” (Measures) tab (see image below).

- / The “Mjere” (Measures) tab displays the “**Prikaži moje mjere**” (Show My Measures) button (see image above).
- / By clicking the “Prikaži moje mjere” (Show My Measures) button, a list of measures will be filtered to show only the measures in which the logged user (in the example above “MZO” -Ministry of Science and Education) will be displayed as “Nositelj mjere” (Measure Implementing authority) or “Sunositelj mjere” (Measure co-Implementing authority).

- 26/ The logged user selects the “Akcijski plan” – > “Pregled akcijskog plana” (Action plan – > Action plan Overview) and then clicks on the “Mjere” (Measures) tab and then “Pregled” (View) button for the selected measure – details of the selected measure are displayed on the screen (see image below).

2.5.1 Podizanje svijesti opće i stručne javnosti o poteškoćama u području zapošljavanja i unapređenje postojećih praksi zapošljavanja mladih pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine

Informacije o mjeri Pokazatelji

Strateško područje 2. Zapošćavanje i uključivanje u gospodarski život

Cilj strateškog područja 2.5. Podiži razinu motivacije pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine za uključivanje na tržište rada

Nositelj Ured za ljudska prava i prava nacionalnih manjina

Provedbe 2019

Suinitelji

- Hrvatska gospodarska komora
- Hrvatska udruga poslodavaca
- Hrvatski zavod za zapošljavanje

Godina praćenja od Nije definirano

Godina praćenja do 2020

Rek 2020.

Iznos predviđenih sredstava 1.160.000,00 kn

Opis sredstava Opis nije unesen

- 27/ By clicking the “Pokazatelji” (Indicators) tab, the indicators for the selected measure are displayed.

2.5.1 Podizanje svijesti opće i stručne javnosti o poteškoćama u području zapošljavanja i unapređenje postojećih praksi zapošljavanja mladih pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine

Informacije o mjeri Pokazatelji

Pokazatelj	Tip	Dodatna dimenzija	Početna vrijednost	Ciljans vrijednost
provedena medijska kampanja	Logički operator	Nema	Ne	Ne
broj održanih radionica i drugih sastanaka i rasprava	Broj	Nema	Da	Da
broj sastanaka s pojedinom grupom dionika	Broj	Nema	Ne	Ne

- / To show the details of the indicator, it is necessary to click the name of the indicator – see the image above.

28/ Once the **the indicator name** is clicked, details of this indicator are displayed – see the image below:

The logged Implementing authority has the option of reviewing additional information related to the indicator:

/ “Rezultati” (**Results**) – show the indicator results (for each of the years of the measure implementation) related to the implementation of the measure, as well as an the initial and the target value (if defined). An example of the display of results is shown in the image below:

/ “Performanse” (**Performance**) – display of key performance indicators that are related to the indicator results, which show the results of the following comparative value indicators:

- / Usporedbu rezultata pokazatelja s početnom vrijednošću (Comparison of the initial value indicators (if defined)),
 - / Usporedbu rezultata pokazatelja s ciljanom vrijednošću (Comparison of the targeted value indicators (if defined)) and
 - / Usporedbu rezultata pokazatelja s prethodnom godinom provedbe akcijskog plana (comparison of the indicator results with the previous implementation year of the Action plan (if such results exist in the system)).
- / An example of the result performance is shown in the image below:

29/ Logged-in users (i.e. “Nositelji” - Implementing authorities), “Sunositelj” (Co-Implementing authorities) and “Administratori” (Administrators) have the option of reviewing the implementation of the Action plan by years. The review begins by selecting “**AKCIJSKI PLAN**” –> “**Pregled provedbe po godinama**” (**ACTION PLAN** –> **Overview of implementation by years**) from the menu – see image to the right:

30/ In the next step, it is necessary to select the year of implementation of the Action plan for which the data will be reviewed – see the image below:

/ The image above shows that the selected implementation year “**2019**” of the Action plan that has the implementation status “Radni” (Operating) (which indicates that it is still possible to change the values related to the respective year of that Action plan implementation).

- / Once selected (mouse click) the year of implementation of the Action plan, the “**Informacije o provedbi**” (**Implementation Information**) tab of the selected Action plan are displayed – see the image below:

- / Once the Action plan is selected (mouse click), it is possible to select the “Mjere) (**Measures**) tab by clicking on them – see the image below:

- / The measures are displayed by using grey boxes that are grouped according to strategic areas and goals. Each grey box contains basic details about the measure, i.e. **identifikacijski broj** (identification number), **naziv mjere** (measure Implementing authority), **naziv nositelja** (Implementing authority name), **rok** (deadline), **broj pokazatelja u mjeri** (number of indicators per measure) and **status mjere** (measure status).
- / Depending on the Implementing authority and the status of the measure, it is possible to initiate certain activities over the measure, namely:

AKCIJA	OPIS
Pogledaj	LOGGED USER ("IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY" OR "CO-IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY") HAS A PERMISSION TO REVIEW THE INFORMATION FOR ALL MEASURES WHICH IMPLEMENTATION HAS BEGUN (I.E. THE MEASURES FOR WHICH THE INFORMATION IS RECORDED IN THE INFORMATION SYSTEM). AFTER REVIEW, THE LOGGED USER (IN THE "IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY" ROLE) WILL HAVE THE PERMISSION TO EDIT THE MEASURES IN WHICH THEY ARE SET AS THE "MEASURE IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY"
Stvori	THE LOGGED USER (IN THE "IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY" ROLE) HAS THE PERMISSION TO INITIATE THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MEASURE, I.E. TO INITIATE THE RECORDS OF THE DATA FOR THOSE MEASURES IN WHICH THEY ARE SET AS "NOSITELJ MJERE" (IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY)
Provedba nije započela	THE LOGGED USER ("IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY" OR "CO-IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY") DOES NOT HAVE THE OPTION TO REVIEW THE DATA FOR ALL MEASURES WHOSE IMPLEMENTATION HAS NOT STARTED IN THOSE MEASURES IN WHICH THEY ARE NOT SET AS THE "NOSITELJ MJERE" (MEASURE IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY).

31/ In case of data review for the measure in which the logged user is designated as the “Nositelj mjere” (Measure Implementing authority).

/ In case the logged-in user is “HZZ” (Croatian Employment Service):

/ In the image on the left we can see that the “HZZ” (Croatian Employment Service) has been set as the Implementing authority for the selected measure, which enables various options to “HZZ” regarding measure implementation.

By clicking on the “**Stvori**” (Create) button, a logged user “HZZ” will see a screen with the option of entering the attribute of the measure shown in the image below:

Mjera 2.2.1. Provoditi senzibilizaciju poslodavaca i informiranje o mogućnostima korištenja mjera za zapošljavanje nezaposlenih osoba romske nacionalne manjine...

Nositelj mjere: Hrvatski zavod za zapošljavanje

Rok: Kontinuirano

Broj pokazatelja: 4

Status mjere: Provedena

Pogledaj

/ After you click the the “Pogledaj” (View) button, the following screen will appear:

Provedba mjere 2.1.1 za 2019. godinu

Provoditi u skladu s potrebama i mogućnostima nezaposlenih osoba romske nacionalne manjine, osobito žena, mladih i dugotrajno nezaposlenih osoba, prilagođene aktivnosti usmjerene na stjecanje i razvijanje vještina, sposobnosti i motivacije za njihovo uključivanje na tržište rada

Informacije o provedbi: Pokazatelji 5, Financijska sredstva 1, Pokazi 1

Uredi, Izvještaj, Zamljučaj

Nositelj	Hrvatski zavod za zapošljavanje
Sunositelji	Nema sunositelja
Pokazatelji	1 od 5
Iznos predviđenih sredstava	12.727.000,00 kn
Utrošena financijska sredstva	789.000,00 kn
Rok	2019
Evaluacija	123
Poslovnica i projekti	406
Status provedbe mjere	Provedena
Pojasnjenje	789

NOTE 1 Since the logged user “HZZ” has the role of the **measure Implementing authority**, in the upper left corner of the screen there are two buttons ([Uredi](#) [Izvještaj](#)), “Uredi” (Edit) has the functionality of editing the measure and “Izvještaj” (Report) that triggers the reporting function (in Croatian) related to the selected measure.

NOTE 2 Since the registered user “HZZ” has the role of **the measure Implementing authority**, in the upper right corner of the screen there is an extra button ([Zamljučaj](#)) which triggers the functionality of locking the implementation of the measure.

- 32/ While continuing to review the data for the measure in which the logged user is set as “Measuring Implementing authority”, click the “**Pokazatelji**” (Indicators) tab, and the following screen will appear:

Provedba mjere 2.1.1 za 2019. godinu

Provođiti u skladu s potrebama i mogućnostima nezaposlenih osoba romske nacionalne manjine, osobito žena, mladih i dugotrajno nezaposlenih osoba, prilagođene aktivnosti usmjerene na stjecanje i razvijanje vještina, sposobnosti i motivacije za njihovo uključivanje na tržište rada

Informacije o provedbi Pokazatelji 5 Financijska sredstva 1 Prilozi 1

broj učenika uključenih u postupak profesionalnog informiranja i savjetovanja prema dobropolu

Vrijednost: 5555

Uredi

broj nezaposlenih osoba uključenih u aktivnosti savjetovanja i aktivacijske programe prema spolukombitiraju nezaposlenosti

Vrijednost pokazatelja još nije unesena.

Doda

- / This screen shows the value of the entered indicators that define the implementation of the selected measure – the example shows that 5555 students enrolled in professional information activities 2019.

NOTE 1 by clicking the “**Uredi**”(Edit) button, an authorized person (e.g. Implementing authority of the measure) can initiate the procedure of updating this number.

NOTE 2 by clicking the “**Uredi**”(Edit) button, an authorized person (e.g. Implementing authority of the measure) can initiate the procedure of entering new indicator value.

- 33/ While continuing to review the data for the measure in which the logged user is set as “Measuring Implementing authority”, click the “**Financijska sredstva**” (Financial resources) tab, and the following screen will appear:

Provedba mjere 2.1.1 za 2019. godinu

Provođiti u skladu s potrebama i mogućnostima nezaposlenih osoba romske nacionalne manjine, osobito žena, mladih i dugotrajno nezaposlenih osoba, prilagođene aktivnosti usmjerene na stjecanje i razvijanje vještina, sposobnosti i motivacije za njihovo uključivanje na tržište rada

Informacije o provedbi Pokazatelji 5 Financijska sredstva 1 Prilozi 1

Doda novu financijsku stavku

Financijska sredstva utrošena za provedbu mjere u 2019. godini i aktivnosti proračuna

Šifra aktivnosti iz proračuna (pozicija)	Iznos	Proračunska sredstva	Švrta i opis
A.792007	125.000,00 kn	Državni proračun	Sredstva osigurana u okviru ...

Drugi izvori financiranja (fondovi EU, ostali donatori)

Program/naziv stavke	Iznos	Donator	Provođitelj	Opis
----------------------	-------	---------	-------------	------

- / The image above shows the records of the financial resources spent for the implementation of the measure in 2019. Financial resources are classified into the “Proračunska sredstva” (Budgetary resources) (shown in the table above) and “Druge izvore financiranja” (Other sources of financing) (shown in the table below).

NOTE by clicking the “**Dodaj novu financijsku stavku**” (**Add new financial item**) button, the authorized person (e.g. the Implementing authority of the measure) may record the new financial resources that were required to carry out the measure. Also, an authorized person can update previously entered data.

- / At the end of data review for the measure in which the logged user is set as “Measuring Implementing authority”, click the “**Prilozi**” (**Attachments**) tab, and the following screen will appear:

- / This screen shows the attachments posted regarding the measure and/or the implementation of the measure. Users who have the right to review the measure can view/download attachments for that measure.

NOTE by clicking the “Dodaj prilog” (**Add Attachment**) button, an authorized person (for example, a measure Implementing authority or co-Implementing authority) can initiate a procedure for adding a new attachment for the selected measure.

- 34/** In case of the review of data for the measure in which the logged user is not designated as the “Nositelj mjere” (Measure Implementing authority).

- / In case the logged-in user is “mzo” (Ministry of Science and Education):
 - / In the image on the left we can see that the “Agencija za odgoj i obrazovanje” (Education Agency) has been set as Implementing authority for the selected measure, giving the user “MZO” the option to view the measure but **not** to edit/enter the measure indicators.

- 35/ By clicking on the “**Pogledaj**” (**View**) button, a logged-in user “MZO” will see a screen with the option of entering the attribute of the measure shown in the image below:

The screenshot shows a web interface for the implementation of measure 1.1.1 for the year 2019. The page title is "Provedba mjere 1.1.1 za 2019. godinu". Below the title, there is a navigation bar with tabs: "Informacije o provedbi", "Poznatelji", "Financijska sredstva", and "Prihodi". The main content area displays the following information:

Nositelj	Agencija za odgoj i obrazovanje
Sunositelji	Nema sunositelja
Pokazatelji	1 od 1
Iznos predviđenih sredstava	4.500,00 kn
Utrošena financijska sredstva	202.000,00 kn
Rok	Kontinuirano
Evaluacija	Evaluacija će biti unesena po završetku provedbe
Postignuća i problemi	Početak provedbe mjere
Status provedbe mjere	Nije provedena
Pojšnjenje	Započeo proces provedbe

- / The screen above shows information on the implementation of the selected measure, similar to step 25.

NOTE Since the logged user “MZO” is **not** set as “Nositelj mjere” (Measure Implementing authority) the following buttons on the screen shown above are **not** available: “Ispis izvještaja” (Print Report), “Uređivanje mjere”, (Edit measure), “Uređivanje pokazatelji”, (Edit indicators), etc.

- 36/ In case of measures whose implementation has not started and where the logged user is a “Measure Implementing authority”.

- / In case the logged-in user is “MZO”:

- / In the image on the left we can see that the “Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja” (Ministry of Science and Education) has been set as the Implementing authority for the selected measure, giving the user “MZO” the option to edit measure/enter the new measure indicators.

- / By clicking on the “**Stvori**” (**Create**) button, a logged-in user “MZO” will see a screen with the option of entering the attribute of the measure shown in the image below:

The screenshot shows the details for measure 1.1.2: "Mjera 1.1.2. Sufinanciranje roditeljskog udjela za pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine u integriranim programima predškolskog odgoja". The information displayed is:

Nositelj mjere:	Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja
Rok:	Kontinuirano
Broj pokazatelja:	1
Status mjere:	Provedba nije započeta

At the bottom right, there is a blue button labeled "Stvori".

- / A part of the screen for the “Nova provedba mjere” (New measure implementation), i.e. the screen for entering attributes of the measure is shown in the following image:

Nova provedba mjere

Akcijski plan: Akcijski plan 2018-2020.

Mjera: sufinansiranje reditajskog učenja za pripremljiva mlađša nacionalna marjine u integriranom programu predškolskog odgoja

Opis provedbe

Postignuća i problemi

Status provedbe mjere

Pojasnjeno

Pojasnjeno na engleskom

Spremi Očistiti

- / When initiating the implementation of a new measure, it will be necessary to enter data related to the evaluation of the measure, achievements and issues related to the measure, the status of the measure and the clarification of the measure.
- / After saving the data related to the new implementation of the measure, the Implementing authority will be able to use functionalities such as “Izvezi izvještaj vezan uz mjeru” (Export Measure Report), “Zaključaj mjeru” (Lock measure), “Uredi mjeru” (Edit measure).

37/ In case of the review of data for the measure whose implementation has **not** started, and in which the logged user is **not** designated as the “Nositelj mjere” (Measure Implementing authority).

/ In case the logged-in user is “MUP” (Ministry of Interior):

/ In the image on the left we can see that the “Ured za ljudska prava i prava nacionalnih manjina” (Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities) has been set as the Implementing authority for the selected measure, which does not enable user “MUP” the option to edit measure/enter the new measure indicators.

/ In the lower part of the box there is the “**Provedba nije započela**” (**Implementation not Started**) button that **cannot be** clicked because the user “MUP” is not the “Implementing authority” and has no right to edit it.

3 / ENTERING MEASURE CONTENT AND INDICATORS FOR THE IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES

The Implementing authority of the measure will login the web interface and record the data related to the measure implementation, namely, enter the measure attribute, enter the indicator values, enter financial data related to the implementation of the measure, add attachments and other actions related to the implementation of the measure. Given that, in practice, most of the Implementing authority's work in the web interface for monitoring the National Roma Inclusion Strategy implementation in the Republic of Croatia will be carried out with this functionality, it is necessary to pay special attention and dedicate enough time to go through all the specifics.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ACTION PLAN MEASURES

- 1/ In the next step, it is necessary to select the year of implementation of the Action plan for which the data will be reviewed – see the image below:

- 2/ After selecting the year of the Action plan implementation, on the screen that will appear, select the **"Provedba mjera"** (Measure implementation) tab (see image below)

- 1/ On the **"Provedba mjera"** (Measure implementation) tab, you can select **"Pokaži moje mjere"** (Show My Measures) button (by clicking the mouse button) to filter the measure box list to show only those measure boxes in which the logged-in user is listed as "Implementing authority".

- 3/ In order to begin the new implementation of the measure, it is necessary to find the measure to which the Implementing authority is a registered user and which has not yet begun.
- / In the image on the left we can see that the “Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja” (Ministry of Science and Education) has been set as Implementing authority for the selected measure, giving the user “mzo” the right to enter measures indicator, i.e. to implement the new measure.
- / By clicking on the “**Stvori**” (**Create**) button, a logged-in user “mzo” will see a screen with the option of entering the attribute of the measure shown in the image below:
- / The “**Nova provedba mjere**” (**New Measure Implementation**) screen looks like this:

- / In order to start with the implementation of a new measure, the basic details of the measure should be recorded, including:
 - / Implementation description,
 - / Achievements and issues related to the measure,
 - / Status of the measure implementation (“Partly implemented”, “Implemented” or “Not implemented”),
 - / Explanations relating to measures (in Croatian and English)
 - / After filling out all the required information, the user should click the **“Spremi” (Save)** button (at the bottom of the screen) to save the data related to the implementation of the measure and to make the implementation visible to all web interface users.
- 4/ After saving the data related to the new measure implementation (see previous step), a screen with details for the measure implementation will be displayed – see the image below:

- / The screen with measure implementation data shown in the image above can be considered as the starting point for data entry related to the measure implementation – see below.

ENTERING THE INDICATOR VALUE

- 5/ The measure should have at least one indicator and may have more indicators. Indicators may be of different types, i.e. they can be simple (e.g. “*Upis broja održanih edukacija*” (Enter the number of education sessions held) “*Zakon je izrađen (da / ne)*” (Act drafted (yes/no) etc.), or complex (e.g. “*Broj održanih edukacija po spolu i dobnim skupinama*” (Number of education sessions held by gender and age groups), “*Broj ostvarenih prava osoba prema spolu*” (Number of realized rights of persons by gender “, etc.).

- / Entry of the indicator value starts on the “**Pokazatelji**” (Indicators) tab – see the image below:

- / Clicking on the “**Dodaj**” (Add) button starts the entry of the indicator value.

NOTE if the indicators for the selected measure are already defined, then the “**Uredi**” (Edit) button will be displayed not the “Dodaj” (Add) button.

- / Depending on the type of indicator and the number of dimensions, a variety of input indicators are available in the web interface, which may include, for example, the following indicator values:

- / The indicator “Usvojen Zakon o izmjenama i dopunama Zakona o međunarodnoj i privremenoj zaštiti” (Act on the Amendments to the Act on International and Temporary Protection) has the type “**Logički operater**” (Logical Operator) and its value needs to be set on “**Da**” (Yes) or “**Ne**” (No).

- / The Indicator “Broj djece romske nacionalne manjine za koje je sufinanciran roditeljski udio” (Number of the Roma national minority children for whom the parental share is co-financed) has the type “**Broj**” (Number) and it is necessary to enter a numerical value that describes the implementation.

ENTERING FINANCIAL ITEMS RELATED TO THE MEASURE IMPLEMENTATION

- 6/ If you want to record the funds spent on the implementation of the measure, you need to select the “**Financijska sredstva**” (**Financial resources**) tab and click the “**Dodaj novu financijsku stavku**”(Add new financial item) button – see the image below:

- 7/ Once you click the “Dodaj novu financijsku stavku”(Add new financial item) button, you will see a basic window for registering a financial item related to the implementation of the measure – see the image below:

- / The web form for registering a new financial item is displayed on the screen (see image above), which will be adjusted depending on the value selection of the “**Izvor financiranja**” (**Funding source**). Possible values that “Izvor financiranja” (Funding source) may have are:
- / “**Državni proračun**” (**State Budget**): the implementation of the measure is financed from the budget and is related to certain/specific budget items,
 - / “**EU fondovi**” (**EU funds**): the implementation of the measure is funded from EU funds,
 - / “**Ostali donatori**” (**Other donors**): the implementation of the measure is funded by other donors.
- / In the first step when adding a new financial item, it is necessary to select the appropriate value in the “Izvor financiranja” (Funding source) – see the following chapters.

- 8/ If the new financial item is set to “Državni proračun” (State Budget) funding, then the web form looks like the image below:

- / A web form that is customized for the use of “Državni proračun” (State Budget) as a source of funding will need to have the following specific attributes :
 - / “Šifra proračunske stavke (pozicija)”(Budget item code (Position)): a unique budget item that can be specified as a position code or as a code and position name
 - / “Vrsta proračuna” (Budget type)²⁶ : it is necessary to choose the type of budget that is used as a source of funding and which can be either “Državni proračun” (State Budget) or “Proračun područja lokalne samouprave” (Local Self-governance area budget).
- / Additionally, **common attributes** for all sources of funding are required:
 - / “Iznos (Amount) means the amount (expressed in kuna) of the funds used from the said source to finance the implementation of the measure
 - / “Svrha i opis” (Purpose and Description) which may include details regarding the financing of the budget measure.

²⁶ The budget type can be edited by editing the values of the “Proračunska sredstva” (Budget resources)

- 9/ If the new financial item is set to “**EU fondovi**” (**EU funds**), then the web form looks like the image below:

- / A web form that is customized for the use of “**EU fond**” (**EU fund**) as a source of funding will need to have the following **specific attributes** :
- / “**Naziv stavke**” (**Item Name**): It is necessary to enter the name and/or code of the financial item from the EU fund from which the funds for implementing the measure were donated
 - / “**Donator**” (Donor)²⁷: it is necessary to choose the institution that has donated the funds to carry out the measure. You can choose from the code list “EU Europska unija” (European Union), “UN Ujedinjeni narodi” (United Nations), “WB (World Bank)” or “Ostalo” (Other).
 - / Additionally, **common attributes** for all sources of funding are required:
 - / “**Iznos** (**Amount**)” means the amount (expressed in kuna) of the funds used from the said source to finance the implementation of the measure
 - / “**Svrha i opis**” (**Purpose and Description**) which may include details regarding the financing of the budget measure.

²⁷ The list of donors can be edited by editing the values in the “**Vrsta donatora**” (Donor type).

- 10/ If the new financial item is set to “**Ostali donatori**” (**Other donors**), then the web form looks like the image below: (see image below)

- / A web form that is customized for the use of “**Ostali donatori**” (**Other donors**) as a source of funding will need to have the following **specific attributes** :
 - / “**Program**”: enter the name of the program from which the donation was received
 - / “**Donator**” (Donor)²⁸: it is necessary to choose the institution that has donated the funds to carry out the measure. You can choose from the code list “EU Europska unija” (European Union), “UN Ujedinjeni narodi” (United Nations), “WB (World Bank)” or “Ostalo” (Other)
 - / “**Provoditelj**” (**Beneficiary**): It is necessary to indicate the name of the institution that carried out the donation.
- / Additionally, **common attributes** for all sources of funding are required:
 - / “**Iznos (Amount)**” means the amount (expressed in kuna) of the funds used from the said source to finance the implementation of the measure
 - / “**Svrha i opis**” (**Purpose and Description**) (in Croatian and English) which may include details regarding the financing of the budget measure.

²⁸ The list of donors can be edited by editing the values in the “**Vrsta donatora**” (Donor type)

INTRODUCTION: ATTACHMENTS LINKED TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MEASURE

When implementing measures, there may be a need to set up various files related to the implementation of the measure, either as a prerequisite for implementing the measure, or as an action that will facilitate/enable the implementation of the measure or as an evidence of the implementation of the measure. Such files, in the form of “**attachments**”, may be uploaded to the web interface and may be available to all Implementing authorities and co-Implementing authorities of the measure.

Examples of possible file types that can be set as attachments are document templates, rulebooks, laws, signature lists, Excel files, graphic logos, etc. Basically, there is no limit on the type of file that can be set as an attachment to the measure.

When setting up and reviewing the attachments in the roles of “Administrator”, “Nositelj” (Implementing authority) and “Sunositelj” (Co-Implementing authority) in the web interface, the following permissions apply:

PERMISSION	ROLE “ADMINISTRATOR “	ROLE “NOSITELJ“ (IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY)	ROLE “SUNOSITELJ“ (CO-IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY)
ADDING A NEW ATTACHMENT TO THE MEASURE	√	√	√
UPDATING YOUR ATTACHMENT (I.E. THE ATTACHMENT THAT THIS USER HAS UPLOADED)	√	√	√
UPDATE ALL ATTACHMENT TO THE MEASURE	√	√	x

OVERVIEW OF ATTACHMENTS RELATED TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MEASURE

To review attachments set with a specific measure, you need to do the following:

- 11/ Log in to the web interface as the **Implementing authority**
- 12/ After logging in, from the application menu select the function “AKCIJSKI PLAN” -> “Pregled provedbe po godinama” (ACTION PLAN -> Annual Implementation report overview)
- 13/ Select the year of the Action plan implementation
- 14/ Click the “Provedba mjera”(Measure implementation) tab, then click the “Prikaži moje mjere” (Show My Measures) button.
- 15/ Click the “Pogledaj” (View) button in the grey box of the measure you want to review (and possibly set) the attachments
- 16/ Click on the “Prilozi” (Attachments) tab to display attachments that are currently set for the selected measure – see the image below:

- 17/ If you want to review a particular attachment (i.e. if you want to download the attached file), you need to click the attachment name – see the image below:

SETTING UP A NEW ATTACHMENT RELATED TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MEASURE

- 18/ On the screen showing the details of the implementation of the measure, i.e. on the “Prilozi” (Attachments) tab inside that screen, click the “Dodaj prilog” (Add attachment) button – see the image below:

- 19/ After clicking the “Dodaj prilog” (Add attachment) button, a screen will appear for adding a new attachment:

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Novi prilog" (New attachment) within a navigation menu that includes "AKCIJSKI PLAN", "OBAVIJESTI", "PORUKE", "INFORMACIJE", and "FORUM". The breadcrumb trail is "Početna / Akcijski plan / Provedba AP / Provedba mjere / Prilog". The form contains a "Datoteka" (File) field with a "Brisanje" (Delete) button, a "Bilješka" (Note) text area, and "Spremi" (Save) and "Odustani" (Cancel) buttons at the bottom.

- / On the screen to add a new attachment, you need to complete the web form to publish the new attachment:
 - / **“Datoteka” (File)** – Click the “Browse” button to select the file to be uploaded to the web interface and which will be set as an attachment to the selected measure
 - / **“Bilješka” (Note)** – it is possible to write down a short description of the purpose of the file that was uploaded as an attachment to the selected measure
- / Once the form fields are filled out, just click the **“Spremi” (Save)** button and the new attachment will be placed in the web interface.

EDIT ATTACHMENTS

Attachments editing permissions (according to the table shown in the subsection “Uvod: prilozi vezani uz provedbu mjere” (Introduction: attachments related to the implementation of the measure)) can be summarized as follows:

- / **Administrator** has a permission to edit all **attachments** in the web interface,
- / **Implementing authorities** have the permission to edit **ALL attachments in their measures**, i.e. in the measures in which they have been assigned the Implementing authority role, and
- / **Co-Implementing authorities** have the permission to edit **THEIR attachments in their measures**, i.e. in the measures in which they have been assigned the Co-Implementing authority role, and

The procedure for editing the attachment is as follows:

- 20/ On the “Prilozi” (Attachments) tab, click the “**Uredi**” (**Edit**) button for the attachment you want to edit – see the image below:

NOTE if no “Edit” button is found within a particular box, this means that the logged user IS NOT ALLOWED to edit this attachment

- 21/ After clicking the “**Uredi**” (Edit) button, the editing screen (i.e. updating) is displayed – see the image below:

- / when editing (i.e., updating) attachments, the following basic functionality is available:
 - / **Zamjena datoteke priloga** (Replace attachment file): by clicking the “Browse” button, it is possible to choose another file that will be attached to the selected measure
 - / **Uređivanje bilješke vezane uz prilog** (**Edit attachment note**): it is possible to make a supplement or change the text under “Note”
- / After the attachment editing is completed, click the “**Spremi**” (**Save**) button.

DELETE ATTACHMENTS

The permission granted for editing also includes the option to delete the attachment. To delete the attachment, follow the procedure below:

- 22/ When updating the attachment, additional functionality is available to delete the entire attachment – see the image below:

- / At the bottom of the editing screen, click the “**Obriši**” (**Delete**) button in the right corner. Clicking on this button starts deleting the attachment of the measure.

- 23/ Once the button “Obriši” (Delete) is clicked, the check-box will be displayed – see the image below:

- / After clicking on the “U redu” (**OK**) button, i.e. after the successful completion of the deletion, the following message will be displayed – see the image below:

Datoteka uspješno izbrisana

4 / LOCKING THE MEASURE (FOR IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES)

Goal of the exercise: The Implementing authority of the measure will log-in to the web interface and will lock the measure. Once the measure is locked, the Implementing authority will check which functionalities in the review and/or editing mode are available for the locked measure.

LOCKING THE MEASURE

24/ In order to start the locking process, it is necessary to find the measure in which the user has been assigned as the “Implementing authority” and which has already begun.

- / In case the logged-in user is “MZO”:
 - / In the image on the left we can see that the “Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja” (Ministry of Science and Education) has been set as Implementing authority for the selected measure, giving the user “MZO” the right to edit measure content and indicators.
 - / By clicking on the “**Pogledaj**” (View) button, a logged user “MZO” will see a screen displaying the information on measure implementation and the measure locking option.

Mjera 1.1.2. Sufinanciranje roditeljskog udjela za pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine u integriranim programima predškolskog odgoja

Nositelj mjere: Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja

Rok: Kontinuirano

Broj pokazatelja: 1

Status mjere: Djelomično provedena

Pogledaj

25/ The screen with information on the measure implementation is shown in the image below:

Početa | Pregled provedbe po godinama | Provedba AP | Provedba SP | Provedba mjere

Provedba mjere 1.1.2 za 2019. godinu

Sufinanciranje roditeljskog udjela za pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine u integriranim programima predškolskog odgoja

Informacije o provedbi | Pokazatelj 1 | Financijska sredstva | Prijazi 1

Uredi | Izvješće | Zatvori

Nositelj Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja

Sudionici

- Jedinice lokalne i područne (regionalne) samouprave
- grad/žest
- županija/žest

Pokazatelji 0 od 1

Iznos predviđenih sredstava 7.500.000,00 kn

Utrošena financijska sredstva 0,00 kn

Rok Kontinuirano

Evalvacija U osnovnoskolskom sustavu i daje se osigurava produženi boravak te posebna pomoć u učenju hrvatskoga jezika za učenike koji ne poznaju ili nedovoljno poznaju hrvatski jezik. To je iznimno važno, budući da navedene aktivnosti predstavljaju preduvjet uspješnog završetka osnovnog obrazovanja te su i dalje potrebni dodatni napori za postizanje adekvatne pripreme učenika za ulazak u obrazovni sustav, ali i uspješno završavanje osnovnog školovanja.

- / By selecting the “**Zaključaj**” (Lock) button the procedure for locking the measure implementation will be initiated and additional confirmations will be required to lock the measure – see the image on the left

- / After clicking the “**U redu**” (OK) button, the measure will be locked and will be marked in the way illustrated by the image below:

- / **No** tools for editing attributes and values of the indicators and attachments and are available.
- / Also, the information that the measure is locked will appear in grey “boxes” with the basic measure details – see the image to the left:
- / The measure reporting tool is only **available** for the locked measure.
- / The fact that the measure is locked means that further modification of the measure and information on its implementation has been disabled, but it is **possible** to review the measure and create reports using the data entered before the measure was locked.

5 / EXPORT MEASURE DATA (FOR IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES)

The measure Implementing authorities will log-in to the web interface and export the previously entered data related to the implementation of the measure in order to facilitate the production of reports on the implementation of the measures from the Action plan.

EXPORT MEASURE DATA

/ The screen with measure implementation detail has the following look (see image below):

Početna / Pregled provedbe po godinama / Provedba AP / Provedba SP / Provedba mjere

Provedba mjere 1.1.2 za 2019. godinu

Sufinanciranje roditeljskog udjela za pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine u integriranim programima predškolskog odgoja

Informacije o provedbi Pokazatelji 1 Financijska sredstva Pilozi 1

Uvod Izvještaj Završetak

Nositelj Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja

Sunositelji

- Jedinice lokalne i područne (regionalne) samouprave
- grad tešanj
- županija tešanj

Pokazatelji 0 od 1

Iznos predviđenih sredstava 7.500.000,00 kn

Utrošena financijska sredstva 0,00 kn

/ On the “Informacije o provedbi” (Implementation Information) tab, there is a (Report) button [Izvještaj](#)

/ By clicking the “**Izvještaj**” (**Report**) button, you will initiate the process of exporting data, i.e. production of reports in Croatian language related to the implementation of the selected measure from the Action plan

- / For example, clicking the “Izveštaj” (**Report**) button will initiate the data export procedure for the selected measure that will be displayed on the following screen:

Ispis
Natrag

OBRAZAC

za izvještavanje o provedbi mjera: Akcijski plan 2018.-2020. u 2019. godini

Strateško područje 1. Obrazovanje	
Mjera 1.1.2. Sufinanciranje roditeljskog udjela za pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine u integriranim programima predškolskog odgoja	
Nositelj	Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja
Banovatelj	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jedinice lokalne i područne (regionalne) samouprave • grad/terit • županija/terit
Planirana financijska sredstva	7.500.000,00 kn
Utrošena financijska sredstva	0,00 kn
Uvjetačija	U osnovnoškolskim sustavima i dalje se osigurava predložni boravak te posebna pomoć u učenju hrvatskoga jezika za učenike koji ne poznaju ili nedovoljno poznaju hrvatski jezik. To je iznimno važno, budući da navedene aktivnosti predstijaju preduvjet uspjeha u završetku osnovnog obrazovanja te su i dalje potrebni dodatni napor za postizanje adekvatne pripreme učenika za ulazak u obrazovni sustav s ciljem osiguranja završetka osnovnog školovanja.
Podstignuća i problemi	Provedbom mjera ranije javno potaknutih dokumenta usmjerenih uključivanju romske nacionalne manjine kao i posljednjeg operativnog dokumenta (Akcijskog plana za provedbu Nacionalne strategije za uključivanje Roma za razdoblje od 2015. do 2019. godine) postignut je značajan napredak u podršci odgoja i obrazovanja djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine njihovim uključivanjem na svim razinama odgojno-obrazovnog sustava.
Status provedbe mjere	Djelomično provedena
Pojedinačje	Uspješno završen rad na razvoju te napredak osnaživanja sustava podrške te uspostavljanje mehanizama koji omogućavaju dostupnost kako predškolskih programa tako i osnovnoškolskih programa i dalje najveći izazov predstavlja osiguravanje uvjeta za inkluziju socijalno integraciju djece te pripremenosti za školu, stjecanje posebnih znanja i vještina za završetak i nastavak obrazovanja te uspostavljanje ravnoteže broja učbenika pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine u odnosu na ostale učbenike.

Pokazatelji

Pokazatelj 1.1.2.1. Broj djece romske nacionalne manjine za koje je sufinanciran i potičijski udio	
Pokazatelj	Vrijednost

Financijska sredstva

Financijska sredstva utrošena za provedbu mjere u 2019. godini i aktivnosti proračuna				
Šifra aktivnosti iz proračuna (pozičja)	Iznos	Vrsta proračuna	Šifra i opis	
Drugi izvori financiranja (fondovi EU, ostali donatori)				
Program/naziv stavka	Iznos	Donator	Provođač	Opis

- / On the screen shown in the image above, the Implementing authority is able to do the following:
 - / Review all data related to the implementation of measures recorded in the information system and displayed on the screen,
 - / Use copy/paste feature to move data related to the measure implementation in the text editing program (e.g. Microsoft Word or similar) to enable/accelerate the creation of reports on the implementation of measures from the Action plan
 - / Use the print function (by clicking the “Ispiši” (**Print**) button in the upper right corner of the screen) to print information on measure implementation either on printer in a PDF file or similar

6 / REVIEW OF AVAILABLE MEASURES AND UPLOADING ATTACHMENTS TO THE MEASURES FOR CO-IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITIES

A user in the role of the “co-Implementing authority” may log into the web interface and review the data related to the implementation of all measures and upload attachments to the measure in which they have been assigned the “co-Implementing authority” role.

REVIEW OF MEASURE IMPLEMENTATION DATA

- 1/ In the next step, it is necessary to select the year of implementation of the Action Plan for which the data on measure implementation will be reviewed – see the image below:

- 2/ After clicking the year “2019” in the example above, you will see a screen with information on the implementation of the Action Plan in the selected year. Clicking on the “Provedba mjera” (**Measure implementation**) tab will display all Action Plan measures in the selected year that are recorded in the web interface.

- 3/ After you click the the “Provedba mjera” (Measure implementation) button, the following screen will appear:

Provedba akcijskog plana "Akcijski plan 2018.-2020." za 2019. godinu

Informacije o provedbi Provedba strateških područja Provedba mjera

Strateško područje 1. Obrazovanje

Cilj 1.1. Podići kvalitetu i učinkovitost obrazovanja djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine te osigurati stjecanje potrebnih znanja i vještina koje će omogućiti osobni razvoj učenika, kao i završavanje osnovnog obrazovanja s ciljem nastavka školovanja te smanjenje razlike između obrazovnih postignuća djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine u odnosu na prosječnu razinu obrazovnih postignuća svih učenika u osnovnoškolskom obrazovanju u Republici Hrvatskoj.

Mjera 1.1.1. Stručno usavršavanje učitelja, stručnih suradnika i suradnika pomoćnika u osnovnim školama

Nositelj mjere: Agencija za odgoj i obrazovanje
 Rok: Kontinuirano
 Broj pokazatelja: 1
 Status mjere: Nije provedena
 Pogledaj

Mjera 1.1.2. Sufinanciranje roditeljskog udjela za pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine u integriranim programima predškolskog odgoja

Nositelj mjere: Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja
 Rok: Kontinuirano
 Broj pokazatelja: 1
 Status mjere: Djelomično provedena
 Pogledaj

⚠ Provedba mjere je završena.

Cilj 1.2. Povećati obuhvat romske djece oba spola predškolskim odgojem i obrazovanjem te podići razinu kvalitete predškolskog odgoja i obrazovanja djece pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine kao dio cjeline ranog obrazovanja djeteta, koji pomaže smanjenju razlika u društvenom podrijetlu i sposobnostima učenja i nastoji što je moguće bolje zadovoljiti djetetove razvojne potrebe te ga uvesti u svijet svesnog učenja.

Mjera 1.2.1. Sufinanciranje programa predškole za djecu pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine

Nositelj mjere: Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja
 Rok: Kontinuirano
 Broj pokazatelja: 1
 Status mjere: Provedena
 Pogledaj

Mjera 1.2.2. Sufinanciranje namjenskog prijevoza od kuće do vrtića/predškole za djecu pripadnike romske nacionalne manjine koja žive u izoliranim, segregiranim...

Nositelj mjere: Ministarstvo znanosti i obrazovanja
 Rok: Kontinuirano
 Broj pokazatelja: 1
 Status mjere: Provedba nije započela
 Provedba nije započela

- / On the image to the left, it is evident that the logged Co-Implementing authority can review the data in ALL measures whose implementation has begun – and these measures can be recognized by the red button “**Pogledaj**” (View) in the lower right corner of the grey box with the measure.
- / On the same image it is evident the one of the measures is locked (indicated by a yellow exclamation mark). Despite the fact that the measure is locked, the Co-Implementing authority has the ability to review its content.

- / On the image on the left we can see that one of the measures has the status “Implementation has not started” – the Co-Implementing authority is not able to view the information on the implementation of such measures because this information has not yet been entered into the web interface.
 - / To review the information about the implementation of the measure started in the selected implementation year, you must click on the “Pregledaj” (Browse) button in the bottom right corner of the grey box.
 - / In the example described in this manual, “Measure 2.5.1 Podizanje svijesti opće i stručne javnosti o poteškoćama u području zapošljavanja i unapređenje postojećih praksi zapošljavanja mladih pripadnika romske nacionalne manjine (Raising awareness of the general and expert public about employment difficulties and improving existing employment practices for young Roma minority members) was selected for review, but some other measures initiated could have been selected as well.
- 4/ After clicking the “Pogledaj” (View) button, a screen will appear with all available information on the implementation of the selected measure – see the image below:

- / For the measure chosen, the Co-Implementing authorities have the option of viewing (BUT NOT EDITING!) the following information:
 - / **Informacije o provedbi mjere (Information on the implementation of the measure),**
 - / **Pokaazatelji provedbe mjere (Indicators of the measure implementation),**
 - / **Financijska sredstva utrošena za provedbu mjere (Financial resources spent on the implementation of the measure), and**
 - / **Priloge mjere (Attachments to measure).**
- / For the selected measure, the Co-Implementing authorities have the ability to create reports by selecting the “Izvještaj” (Report) button.

NOTE The reviewing process of all the above information related to the implementation of the measure is described in detail in the previous worksheets.

With the ability to review all data on the implementation of all measures as described in the previous section, the “Co-Implementing authorities” have the authorisation to add new attachments ONLY to those measures in which they are officially assigned as “Co-Implementing authorities”.

For a Co-Implementing authority to add a new attachment to their “own” measure, the following procedure must be applied:

- 5/ Once the Co-Implementing authority is logged in, from the application menu select the function “AKCIJSKI PLAN” -> “Pregled provedbe po godinama” (ACTION PLAN -> Annual implementation report overview)
- 6/ In the next step, it is necessary to select the year of implementation of the Action Plan for which the adding of the new attachment to the specific measure will be done:
- 7/ After clicking the year, you will see a screen with information on the implementation of the Action Plan in the selected year.
- / In order to display only the measure in which the logged user is assigned to the Co-Implementing authority role the “Prikaži moje mjere” (Show My Measures) button must be selected.
- 8/ After you click the “Prikaži sve mjere” (Show all measures) button, the following screen will appear (see image below):

- / The screen shown in the image above shows that the logged user is assigned as a Co-Implementing authority only in one measure – the example above, i.e. the measure 1.2.1.

- / If there is a need to show all the measurements, then click the “Prikaži sve mjere” (Show all measures) button at the top of the screen.
 - / Above the grey box with the measures, you can see the information about the strategic area and the objective to which the measure belongs. In case when the screen shows multiple boxes with measure, all of them will be displayed within the appropriate objectives and strategic areas.
 - / Clicking the “**Pogledaj**” (**View**) button, a screen will appear with all available information on the implementation of the selected measure:
- 9/ On the screen showing information about the implementation of the selected measure, select (by clicking the mouse) the “**Prilozi**” (**Attachments**) tab – see the image below:

- / On the “Prilozi” (Attachments) tab, you can see a list of all the attachments that were added to the selected measure up to that moment. The image in the example above shows that only one attachment is currently added to the selected measure. To add a new attachment, select the “**Dodaj prilog**” (**Add Attachment**) function.
- 10/ After clicking the “Dodaj prilog” (Add attachment) button, a screen will appear for adding a new attachment:

- 11/ After the mandatory selection of the attachment file (by clicking on the “Browse” button) and the optional description entry, a text note describing the attachment is saved by clicking on the “**Spremi**” (**Save**) button. In the “**Prilozi**” (**Attachments**) tab, see the following list of attachments:

- / The image on example above shows that there are now two attachments added to the selected measure implementation, one of which (in the example above, the attachment with the title “VARIJABLE DUGOTRAJNOG PRAĆENJA PO PODRUČJIMA I SPECIFIČNIM CILJEVIMA NSUR.docx” (LONG-TERM MONITORING VARIABLES BY AREAS AND SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF NRIS.docx) added by the “**administrator**” and the other (in the example above, it is the attachment titles “rev2_Verzija za rad AP 2018-2020 15022018doc.doc” (rev2_working version AP 2018-2020 15022018doc.doc)) added by the co-Implementing authority “**CZSS**”. The web interface records the **date** and **time** when the attachment was added – this information is visible in the example above and marked with the following ge:
- / By repeating the procedure described in this chapter, it is possible to add as many attachments as you wish on the implementation of the measure.

EDITING THE ATTACHMENT TO THE MEASURE BY CO-IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY

For security reasons, the co-Implementing authorities of the measure have permission to edit THEIR own attachments (i.e., the attachments they added to their measures, i.e. the measures in which they are assigned the role of a co-Implementing authority) - for details on permissions for editing attachments, see the table in the subsection “Uvod: prilozi vezani uz provedbu mjere” (Introduction: attachments related to the implementation of the measure).

/ If the “Edit” button is found within a particular box, this means that the logged user is ALLOWED to edit this attachment. The example in the image above shows that the logged in user has permission to edit the attachment under the title “ rev2_Application AP 2018-2020 15022018doc.doc ”.

12/ Editing attachments by Co-Implementing authority is done in the same way as editing of the attachments by the Implementing authority. After clicking the “**Uredi**” (Edit) (see the image on the previous page) button, the editing (i.e. updating) screen is displayed – see the image below:

- / when editing (i.e., updating) attachments, the following basic functionalities are available to the Co-Implementing authorities:
 - / **Zamjena datoteke priloga** (Replace attachment file): by clicking the “Browse” button, it is possible to choose another file that will be attached to the selected measure
 - / **Uređivanje bilješke vezane uz prilog (Edit attachment note)**: it is possible to make a supplement or change the text under “Note”
- / After the attachment editing is completed, click the “**Spremi**” (**Save**) button.

EDITING ATTACHMENTS BY THE ADMINISTRATOR OR CO-IMPLEMENTING AUTHORITY

In accordance with the permissions for editing the attachments, the attachments to the measures may be edited by the Administrator and the Implementing authorities:

- / **Administrator** has a permission to edit all **attachments** in the web interface,
- / **Implementing authorities of the measure** have the permission to edit **ALL attachments in their measures**, i.e. in the measures in which they have been assigned the Implementing authority role.

The procedure for editing an attachment is identical to the procedure described in the previous chapters of this document.

In order to preserve the credibility of the information in the web interface, when editing the attachment, information about who and when edited the attachment will be recorded – and the information will be available to all web interface users.

For example, if the Implementing authority or the measure the attachment that was previously set by the Co-Implementing authority, then the following information will be displayed when displaying the attachment to the measure – see the image below:

In the image shown in the example above, it can be seen that the attachment “Rev2_Verzija za rad AP 2018-2020 15022018doc.doc” (Rev2_Working version AP 2018-2020 15022018doc.doc) is edited – because the user name of the person who edited the attachment was recorded (in the image above, it is shown that the user name is “**MZO**” and has the role of the measure Implementing authority). Additionally, you can see the **date** and **time** when the attachment was last edited. The attachment editing information are shown on the screen with the following image:

NOTE depending on the sensitivity level of the information stored in the web interface, only the LAST information on the attachment editing will be recorded. Specifically, if the attachment was edited (in this order) by “Person A”, “Person B” and “Person C”, then only the details of the “Person C” will be shown in the web page.

7 / OVERVIEW OF THE EUROPEAN UNION FRAMEWORK AND LINKING THE ATTACHMENTS TO THE ASSESSMENT OF THE THEMATIC AREA

Implementing authorities and co-Implementing authorities (and those who do not participate in the AP implementation, classified as “Users”) can log into the web interface and complete the attachment uploading procedure for the thematic area.

REVIEW OF THE EU FRAMEWORK DATA

- 1/ Select the “Okvir EU” (EU Framework) function to open the EU Framework and the relevant thematic areas.

The screenshot displays the NSRF (Nacionalni sklad za regionalni razvoj) website interface. The main navigation bar includes 'NSRF', 'AKCIJSKI PLAN', 'OKVIR EU', 'PORUKE', 'INFORMACIJE', and 'FORUM'. The page title is 'Godine procjene tematskih područja za Upitnik Europske komisije' (Annual assessment of thematic areas for the Commission questionnaire).

Two buttons are visible for the assessment years: '2018' (labeled 'Za procjenu 2018') and '2019' (labeled 'Nova godina procjene').

The 'Tematska područja' (Thematic areas) section is active, showing 'Tematsko područje 01. Učinkovite mjere politike' (Thematic area 01. Effective policy measures). Below this, there are two paragraphs of text providing context for the assessment, mentioning the Roma Inclusion Strategy and the need for effective measures.

The next section is 'Tematsko područje 02. Pristup obrazovanju' (Thematic area 02. Access to education), which contains a list of nine specific measures (Mjera 01 to Mjera 09). Each measure is presented in a card format with a description and a 'Pregled' (View) button:

- Mjera (a)** ubriniti sepostojanje u skladu s...
- Mjera (b)** ubriniti sve slučajeve nepripremenog smještavanja romskih učenika u škole za učenje s posebnim potrebama
- Mjera (c)** smanjiti opseg ranog napuštanja školovanja (7) na svim razinama obrazovanja, uključujući srednjoškolsko razinu i strukovno obrazovanje
- Mjera (d)** povećati pristup i kvalitetu obrazovanja i skrbi o ranom otkrivanju, uključujući cijenu potpora, ukoliko je to potrebno
- Mjera (e)** ubriniti u obitelji posebne pojedinih učenika i promijeniti ih (uklanjati, u bliskoj suradnji s njihovim obiteljima
- Mjera (f)** koristiti uključujuće i po mjeri sadržajne metode poučavanja i učenja, uključujući podršku u učenju za učenike koji otežano uče, suzbijati nepismenost...
- Mjera (g)** poticati učestvovanje Roma u srednjem i visokom obrazovanju te njegovo završavanje
- Mjera (h)** poboljšati pristup drugoj prilici za obrazovanje i obrazovanje odraslih, pružajući potporu za prijelaz između razina obrazovanja i potporu za stjecanje...

- 2/ In the next step, it is necessary to select the year of implementation (in this case, 2018) of the Action Plan for which the data on measure implementation will be reviewed – see the image below:

- 3/ After clicking the year “2018” in the example above, you will see a screen with information on the assessment of the thematic areas in the selected year.

NOTE in the example above, the assessment of the thematic area has only started for “Pristup obrazovanju” (Access to education). Overview, and, therefore, uploading attachments is only possible for the specified thematic area.

- 4/ Select the “**Pregled**” (Overview) function to open the display of thematic area assessment information.

- / The image above shows the information on the assessment of the thematic area and the tabs “**Procjena mjera EK**” (Assessment of EC measures) and “**Prilozi**”(Attachments). The manual below describes how to add attachments to the “**Prilozi**” (Attachment) tab that is identical to the AP implementation measure.

SETTING UP A NEW ATTACHMENT ON THE ASSESSMENT OF THE THEMATIC AREA

With the ability to review all information on the assessment of the thematic area described in the previous chapter, the logged users (regardless of the role) have the ability to upload new attachment ONLY to those thematic areas for which the assessment is started.

In order to delete the attachment, following the procedure below:

- 5/ After logging in, from the application menu select the function “**Okvir EU**” (EU Framework).
- 6/ In the next step, it is necessary to select a year of the thematic area assessment.
- 7/ After you click the year, the screen with thematic areas and the “**Pregled**” (Overview)” option will be displayed within the area for which the assessment was started in that year.

- 8/ Once the button “Pregled” (Overview) is clicked, the check-box will be displayed (see the image below):

- 9/ On the screen shown above, you need to select the “Prilozi” (Attachments) tab to open the new attachment display – see the image below:

- 1/ On the “Prilozi” (Attachments) tab, you can see a list of all the attachments that were added to the selected measure up to that moment (if such attachments exist, otherwise there will be a note “Nema priloga” (No attachments)). The image in the example above shows that there are no attachments for that thematic area. To add a new attachment, select the “Dodaj priloga” (Add Attachment) function.

- 10/ After clicking the “Dodaj prilog” (Add attachment) button, a screen will appear for adding a new attachment:

- 11/ After the mandatory selection of the attachment file (by clicking on the “Browse” button) and the optional description entry, a text note describing the attachment is saved by clicking on the “**Spremi**” (Save) button. In the “**Prilozi**” (Attachments) tab, see the following list of attachments:

- / The image in the example above shows that there is one attachment for the selected assessment. The web interface records the **date** and **time** when the attachment was added – this information is visible in the example above and marked with the following image:
- / By repeating the procedure described in this chapter, it is possible to add as many attachments as you wish on the thematic area assessment.

The procedure for editing the attachment is as follows:

- 12/ On the “Prilozi” (Attachments) tab, click the “**Uredi**” (**Edit**) button for the attachment you want to edit – see the image below:

- 13/ After clicking the “**Uredi**” (**Edit**) button, the editing screen (i.e. updating) is displayed – see the image below:

- / when editing (i.e., updating) attachments, the following basic functionality is available:
 - / **Zamjena datoteke priloga** (Replace attachment file): by clicking the “Browse” button, it is possible to choose another file that will be attached to the selected measure
 - / **Uređivanje bilješke vezane uz prilog** (**Edit attachment note**): it is possible to make a supplement or change the text under “Note”
- / After the attachment editing is completed, click the “**Spremi**” (**Save**) button.

DELETE ATTACHMENTS

In order to delete the attachment, following the procedure below:

- 14/ When updating the attachment, additional functionality is available to delete the entire attachment – see the image below:

- / At the bottom of the editing screen, click the “**Obriši**” (**Delete**) button in the right corner. Clicking on this button starts deleting the attachment of the measure.

- 15/ Once the button “Obriši” (Delete) is clicked, the check-box will be displayed – see the image below:

- / After clicking on the “U redu” (**OK**) button, i.e. after the successful completion of the deletion, the following message will be displayed - see the image below:

Datoteka uspješno izbrisana

- 1/ European Commission, *An EU Framework for National Roma Integration Strategies up to 2020*, COM(2011) 173/4, Brussels, 2011, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0173&from=EN> (21.5.2018.)
- 2/ Europska komisija, *KOMUNIKACIJI KOMISIJE EUROPSKOM PARLAMENTU I VIJEĆU, Revizija Okvira EU-a za nacionalne strategije integracije Roma u sredini programskog razdoblja*, 2017, str. 2-3, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/HR/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0458&from=HR>, (5.7.2018.)
- 3/ Europski Revizorski Sud, *Političke inicijative i financijska potpora EU-a za integraciju Roma: tijekom posljednjeg desetljeća postignut je znatan napredak, ali potrebni su dodatni naponi na terenu*, br 14, 2016., https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/SR16_14/SR_ROMA_HR.pdf (5.7.2018.)
- 4/ Friedman, E., Horvat, M., *Evaluacijsko izvješće: Evaluation of the National Strategy of the Republic of Croatia for Roma Inclusion*, Zagreb, Office for Human Rights and Rights of National Minorities, UNDP Office of Croatia, 2015
- 5/ Kekez Koštro, A., *Što se misli pod implementacijom javnih politika?*, *Političke analize*, 2015, br. 13, str. 65-67.
- 6/ Kresnaliyska, G., *Monitoring of Public Policies - A Modern Tool of Good Governance*, *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, god.5, br. 5, 2015, str 43-47.
- 7/ Širinić, D., *Priručnik za praćenje javnih politika za organizacije civilnog društva*, Centar za mir, nenasilje i ljudska prava – Osijek, Osijek, 2016., str 27.
- 8/ Vlada Republike Hrvatske, *Nacionalna strategija za uključivanje Roma, za razdoblje od 2013. do 2020. godine*, Zagreb, studeni, 2012., <https://pravamanjina.gov.hr/UserDocImages/arhiva/Nacionalna%20strategija%20za%20ukljucivanje%20Roma%20za%20razdoblje%20od%202013.%20-%202020.pdf> (27. 5. 2018)
- 9/ Vlada Republike Hrvatske, *Akcijski plan za provedbu Nacionalne strategije za uključivanje Roma, za razdoblje od 2013. do 2015. godine*, Zagreb, 2013., https://pravamanjina.gov.hr/UserDocImages/arhiva/Akcijski_plan_za_provedbu_nsUR_za_razdoblje%202013-2015.pdf (23.5.2018.)

EUROPEAN UNION

GOVERNMENT OF THE
REPUBLIC OF CROATIA
Office for Human Rights and
Rights of National Minorities

CENTRE FOR PEACE STUDIES

ECORYS

IPA 2012

Fulfilling conditions for Roma integration on the local/
regional and the national level. This publication was made
with financial support from the European Union and the
Government Office for Human Rights and the Rights of
National Minorities.